

Review

Recent advances in Metal-Organic Framework-Based fiber optic sensors and Photodetectors: Synthesis, Properties, and applications

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ABSTRACT

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are a type of material, consisting of an organic linker and an inorganic metal ion or cluster, that can form highly ordered crystalline structures when combined with organic additives. There are a number of features that are unique to these materials, including their unique hybrid structure, which enables them to have remarkably high surface areas, tunable pore sizes, and personalized functionalities. Several of these characteristics make MOFs particularly attractive for a wide range of applications such as selective gas absorption, sensors, photodetectors etc. As a result, MOFs are being integrated into fiber optic sensors and photodetectors to enable new advances. The focus of the review is on the use of sensors for the monitoring of environmental conditions that require high sensitivity, selectivity, and adaptability. In this review, the authors provide an in-depth examination of the synthesis processes of MOFs for fiber optic sensors and photodetectors, focusing particularly on how these processes affect the structural properties of the MOFs themselves. In order to meet the specific demands of diverse sensor and photodetector applications, the synthesis strategies discussed in this article are critical to tailoring the materials in order to meet their individual characteristics. As well as examining the key properties of MOFs that contribute to their success in sensing applications, the review also examines the factors that contribute to their performance, such as their porous structure, their ability to be tuned in terms of pore size, and their chemical and mechanical stability. A MOF's biocompatibility and reproducibility are essential for potential applications in biomedical and environmental monitoring, and these properties ensure that MOFs perform optimally under a variety of conditions. In addition, we briefly discuss the different application aspects of MOFs for industrial sensing applications as they have the capability to operate in harsh environments, providing valuable insight into process control, and process safety. The MOF-based fiber optic technologies have made tremendous strides in recent years, but there are a number of challenges such as long-term stability, reproducible synthesis, scalability and cost effective integration must be overcome for their full potential to be realized. In spite of these challenges, MOFs based sensors and photodetectors are poised to become essential tools for a range of applications as synthesis methods, material stability, and device integration improve. It provides insight into MOFs' current capabilities and future prospects for innovative sensing solutions for researchers and engineers working on MOF-based technologies.

1. Introduction

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as a captivating class of materials with versatile applications, owing to their unique structural features and tunable properties [1,2]. The amalgamation of organic ligands with metal nodes in MOFs results in a porous crystalline structure, characterized by large surface areas and intriguing

functionalities. A variety of fields have been affected by this, including gas storage, catalysis, drug delivery, and light sensing and detection [3–10]. Here, fiber optic sensors have gained prominence due to their inherent advantages, including high sensitivity, fast response times, and immunity to electromagnetic interference. By using fiber optic sensors for signal transmission, they are able to shield the system from electromagnetic interference and minimize background noise as well, since

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they rely on photons instead of electrons as carriers for signal transmission. With these sensors, information can be transmitted over long distances with minimal loss, making them ideal for a variety of applications that require information to be transmitted over long distances. With their compact and lightweight design, these devices are able to easily integrate into advanced communication networks and a wide variety of medical equipment, making them a powerful addition to any medical facility [2]. As a result of these unique characteristics, fiber optic sensors are critical components in industries requiring precision, reliability, and high performance. The integration of MOFs into this sensing paradigm introduces a new dimension, offering opportunities for enhanced selectivity, improved sensitivity, and tailored functionality.

In addition, due to their versatile and customizable structures, as well as functionalized characteristics, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as highly promising materials for sensor applications [11]. MOFs can be precisely modified to meet the specific requirements of different types of sensors by fine-tuning the composition of metal ions, clusters, and organic ligands. For instance, lanthanide metal ions can be incorporated into MOFs to create luminescent frameworks that are suitable for optical sensors. In addition, functional nanomaterials have been successfully integrated into MOFs to enhance their specificity and efficiency. By integrating MOF composites with other technologies, such as optical, electrochemical, mechanical, and photo-electrochemical sensors, this restores and synergizes their unique properties. [12,13]. Yao et al. developed a highly efficient chemiresistor gas sensor by coating ZnO nanowires with a uniform hydrophobic and catalytic ZIF-CoZn thin film coating. [14]. A nanostructured metal oxide was combined with MOFs for superior selectivity and catalytic activity. Through nucleation and growth of ZIF-CoZn thin films, the ZnO nanowires, whose diameters ranged from 50 to 100 nm, served as templates for the synthesis. It was found that ZnO@ZIF-CoZn nanowires had exceptional acetone sensing performance in comparison to bare ZnO

nanowire exhibiting a detection limit as low as 0.0019 ppm and a range of operation of 0.25 to 2100 ppm.

Interestingly, MOF-based optical sensors have attracted considerable attention due to their improved sensitivity and performance. According to Sugikawa et al., gold nanorods can be encapsulated in MOF-5 nanocrystals by a simple solution-based method (AuNR@MOF-5). [15]. With this design, the sensitivity of surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) for detecting analytes is significantly increased. A millionfold amplification of Raman scattering signals occurred when analytes were adsorbed onto gold nanorods. SERS sensors for small pyridine molecules and their derivatives were further enhanced and made reproducible by the MOF-5 shell, which served as a molecular sieve and prevented aggregation. Through confined surface plasmon resonance, Kreno et al. enhanced the gas detection capabilities of Ag nanoparticle sensors using HKUST-1 coatings, demonstrating how precise MOF synthesis improves sensor performance. [16].

Besides sensor technology, ongoing research focuses on miniaturizing photodetector designs in order to achieve superior performance metrics like quantum efficiency, responsiveness, noise-equivalent power (NEP), and detectivity. MOFs, which combine organic and inorganic compositions, have a large surface area, a high porosity, and a highly adaptable structural composition, making them ideal as active materials in photodetectors. In addition to being stable and efficient, these properties allow for the development of devices that detect light over a broad spectrum, such as those that detect X-rays or near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths. [17,18].

Here, in this paper we provide a comprehensive overview of the recent developments in MOF-based fiber optic sensors. We delve into the fundamental principles underlying both MOFs and fiber optic sensing technologies, elucidating the synergies that arise from their integration. The review encompasses a discussion on MOF key properties influencing sensor performance, and notable applications in the realm of fiber optic sensing (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Application of MOF based fiber optic sensors.

The initial sections of this review delve into the foundational aspects of MOFs, shedding light on their diverse properties, and sensing techniques, that make them conducive to sensor applications. Furthermore, we emphasize the principles that govern their operation and their advantages over traditional sensing approaches. As we navigate through the intricate landscape of MOF-based fiber optic sensors, specific attention is given to notable achievements and breakthroughs in recent research. The discussion encompasses case studies highlighting the successful implementation of MOFs in diverse sensing scenarios, including environmental monitoring, biomedical applications, and industrial sensing. The interdisciplinary nature of this research is underscored by examining the interplay between chemistry, materials science, and photonics. MOFs, with their tailored functionalities, bring a new level of sophistication to fiber optic sensors, allowing for precise tuning to specific analytes, improved detection limits, and expanded application domains. In the following section, MOF based photodetectors, their classification and preparation methodologies have been discussed. In the concluding sections, we offer insights into future prospects and challenges associated with the continued exploration of MOF-based fiber optic sensors and photonic devices like photodetectors. We anticipate that this review will serve as a valuable resource for researchers, engineers, and practitioners seeking to harness the synergies between MOFs and fiber optic sensing for innovative and efficient sensing solutions.

2. Fundamental properties of MOF material

2.1. Porosity

The large specific surface area and porosity (fraction of void volume to total volume) of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are two of its most crucial characteristics, which have prompted sensing applications. There are many binding sites for analytes due to the enormous interior surface area of MOFs, which raises the likelihood of analyte-MOF interactions. In MOF-based fibre optic sensors, this better interaction may result in increased sensitivity and selectivity. [19,20].

For example, Shearer et al. provided a comprehensive explanation of the defect chemistry associated with UiO-66 materials synthesized under typical conditions, emphasizing the inclusion of mono-carboxylic acid modulators during the process. This study offers insights that could be broadly applicable to the synthesis of “Zr6 MOFs”. [20]. Connolly et al., on the other hand, explored the formation of Zr-UiO-66, which is recognized as one of the most stable MOFs, developed without the need for binders or external pressure. [19]. Their work demonstrated the production of monoliths characterized by significant bulk density and notable microporosity, with dimensions extending to the centimeter scale. They also detailed how the macrostructure of these monoliths incorporates adjustable, narrow mesoporous volumes, which play a crucial role in optimizing pore-size distribution to enhance gas uptake efficiency. For gases like methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), the tailored mixed meso/microporous monoliths exhibited Type II adsorption isotherms, achieving standard volumetric working capacities. By refining the pore-size distribution (PSD) to integrate precisely controlled volumes of narrow mesoporosity, the performance of UiO-66, which inherently has a weaker interaction with CH₄ at low pressures, was significantly enhanced. This optimization achieved a volumetric CH₄ working capacity of 172 cm³ (STP) at 100 bar, marking an 11 % improvement compared to the benchmark monoHKUST-1 material [19]. This breakthrough represents a pivotal advancement in the design of robust, air-stable MOFs tailored for commercial gas storage applications.

2.2. Tunable pore size

For selective sensing applications, the ability to precisely regulate MOF pore size is a major benefit. The various organic linker lengths cause the variation in pore size. By tailoring the pore size to match the

dimensions of specific analytes, MOFs can selectively capture and interact with these analytes, while rejecting other substances [21,22].

Liang et al. successfully developed a series of water-stable zirconium-tricarboxylate frameworks, denoted as [Zr₆O₄(OH)₄(X)₆(btc)₂]_nH₂O, where the X group represented monocarboxylate ligands such as formate (F), acetate (A), and propionate (P). The frameworks exhibited tunable porosity due to systematic modulation of the chain length of the monocarboxylate ligands [22]. This capability to adjust pore size not only modifies the intrinsic porosity of the framework but also presents an important strategy for designing mixed-linker MOFs with diverse properties. Similarly, Meng et al. developed three isostructural Co-based MOF-74-III materials with enlarged pores by tailoring the side chains on the ligand, achieving precise control over pore diameters of 2.6, 2.4, and 2.2 nm. [21]. Gas sorption analyses revealed that highly mesoporous materials with ligands containing fused benzene rings on both sides induced steric hindrance, which limited the accessibility of open Co(II) sites and reduced their effectiveness in enhancing gas uptake. Conversely, ligands with fused benzene rings on one side allowed additional anchoring sites for CO₂ molecules through π - π interactions, significantly improving CO₂ adsorption capacity as well as CO₂/CH₄ and CO₂/N₂ selectivity. This work underscores the potential of structural and chemical modifications in ligands to tailor gas storage and separation properties in MOFs.

2.3. Chemical tenability

Changing the metal nodes and organic linkers in MOFs can change their chemical makeup, which can change the bonding and surface features of the MOF. Improved sensitivity and specificity in MOF-based fibre optic sensors can result from this surface chemistry modification, which can also improve the interaction between the MOF and target analytes. [23,24].

According to Afrin et al., the chemical stability of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) is primarily influenced by exposure to water vapor and liquid water [23]. The inherent chemical vulnerabilities in MOFs arise from the metal-ligand coordination or the nodes within the framework, which can undergo hydrolysis. This process leads to the protonation of the ligand and the formation of a node that is either bound to water or hydroxide ions. The rate at which these hydrolyzed forms occur is higher in acidic environments, which promote the formation of hydroxide-ligated nodes, while basic solutions tend to produce water-ligated nodes. In the case of Zr-MOFs, the Zr-oxo cluster and the carboxylate linker form strong coordination bonds, contributing significantly to the exceptionally high chemical stability of these materials. Notably, the quaternization of pyridyl groups on organic linkers can alter the electronic structure of these linkers, providing new pathways for tuning the chemical properties of the resulting MOFs. [23].

Burrows et al. highlighted the wide array of applications for MOFs that have undergone post-synthetic modification (PSM). [24]. Since the building blocks of MOFs are highly reactive and can be tailored through modification, PSM offers a versatile approach for designing MOFs with specific functionalities. This approach allows for the creation of functionalized MOFs that may not be achievable using conventional synthetic methods. Compared to their unmodified counterparts, these modified MOFs often exhibit enhanced properties, such as improved gas adsorption, catalytic activity, sequestration capabilities, and biological functions. In a notable example, Zhang et al. developed a new fluorescent probe, UiO-66-PSM, by functionalizing UiO-66-N3 with phenylacetylene through a copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne click reaction (CuAAC) [25]. Among various metal ions, Hg²⁺ displayed the most pronounced fluorescence response, demonstrating rapid reaction times, exceptional selectivity, and high sensitivity. The click-generated triazole unit acted as a binding site for Hg²⁺, allowing for its detection in environmental water samples without compromising the structural integrity of the MOF. This work underscores the significant potential of MOFs in practical applications, particularly in environmental monitoring.

2.4. Mechanical stability

For MOFs to be used in fibre optic sensors over the long term, their mechanical stability is essential. To guarantee that the MOF's sensing capabilities hold steady throughout time, its structural integrity must be preserved. When exposed to ambient conditions, MOFs usually show exceptional mechanical stability. However, in harsh environments, like high temperatures or extremely high pH, some MOFs may degrade. [26–28].

Cao et al. detailed the development of gas-sensitive coatings for single-mode and multi-mode optical fibers by incorporating polymer/nanocrystalline Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) composites as methane (CH₄) sensors for monitoring natural gas infrastructure [26,27]. The study utilized PDMS-based silicone polymers, known for their enhanced mechanical and optical properties, as host materials for the widely used MOF ZIF-8. The addition of ZIF-8 nanocrystals into the PDMS matrix altered the physical characteristics of the material, notably enhancing its permeability and CH₄ solubility. These modifications led to improved sensor performance, with both multimode fibers and D-shaped single-mode fibers achieving a methane detection limit of 1 % in nitrogen (N₂) gas. [26]. This development marks a significant step forward in the application of MOFs in environmental monitoring and natural gas safety. In the context of material science, defects introduced into crystalline materials are recognized as a valuable means of fine-tuning the properties of materials across various domains. Dissegna et al. conducted an innovative study using high-pressure powder X-ray diffraction analysis to explore the response of defective UiO-66 to hydrostatic pressure, varying pressures from ambient conditions to 0.4 GPa in steps of 0.025 GPa. [28]. Their findings revealed that the modulus of the defective UiO-66 decreased under pressure, with amorphization occurring in the samples at approximately 0.2 GPa. Interestingly, no direct correlation was found between the bulk modulus of the defective UiO-66(Zr) samples and the concentration of defects, highlighting the complex nature of defect incorporation within the framework and the challenges of predicting how defects influence material behavior under stress. [28]. This study provides deeper insights into the structural and mechanical properties of MOFs and their potential applications in high-pressure environments.

2.5. Biocompatibility

MOFs used in biomedical applications must exhibit excellent biocompatibility, i.e. They should not cause any toxic or harmful effects on biological systems. The use of non-toxic and biocompatible organic linkers is crucial for ensuring the safety of these sensors in biomedical settings. The coordination metal and the organic linker characteristics, as well as their general physical attributes including size, shape, and surface charge, all affect biocompatibility. [29–34].

Chiavaioli et al. developed a sol-gel based titania-silica-coated long period grating (LPG) for an evanescent wave optical fiber biosensor, demonstrating a detection limit of 10⁻¹¹ M for IgG/anti-IgG detection on this structured LPG. [30]. The unique porous architectures of MOFs have emerged as promising candidates for encapsulating enzymes, owing to their ability to provide a stable and efficient environment for biological molecules. In a significant advancement, Zhu et al. introduced glucose oxidase (GOx)-encapsulated zeolitic imidazole-based MOFs (ZIF-8) integrated with long period gratings (LPGs) to create highly stable, label-free optical fiber biosensors for glucose sensing. [35]. The composite materials were synthesized using precursor solutions with varying concentrations of GOx, Zn²⁺, and 2-methylimidazole, resulting in different morphologies. These composites displayed excellent enzymatic activity and stability under challenging conditions, alongside high protein encapsulation efficiency. The ZIF-8 MOF not only acted as a protective shell for the GOx but also functioned as an analyte collector on the optical fibers. The resulting sensor exhibited a response coefficient of approximately 0.5 nm/mM, with a linear relationship between the

wavelength shifts and glucose concentrations in the range of 1–8 mM, highlighting the potential of MOFs for sensitive and reliable biosensing applications. [35].

In addition to their work on glucose sensing, Zhu et al. also explored a novel tapered single-mode coreless single-mode (SCS) structure, which demonstrated high sensitivity for refractive index sensing. [29]. To further enhance the specificity of optical biosensors, they developed an enzyme encapsulation film by embedding urease within a ZIF-8 framework using an in situ growth technique on coreless optical fibers. This approach enabled precise and online monitoring of urease binding, facilitating real-time measurement of urea concentration. The refractive index changes caused by urease binding induced corresponding shifts in the optical fiber's wavelength, and the sensor demonstrated a sensitivity of 0.8 mM/RIU (refractive index unit) with a detection limit of 0.1 mM. The resonance wavelength exhibited a strong linear correlation with urea concentrations in the range of 1 to 10 mM, when the sensor was operated with broadband light between 1525 nm and 1590 nm. [29]. This innovative method showcases the potential of MOF-based optical fiber biosensors for highly specific, real-time biological monitoring with excellent sensitivity and low detection limits.

2.6. Reproducibility

For fibre optic sensors to operate consistently, MOF synthesis and material characteristics must be reproducible. Researchers can create MOF-based sensors that offer precise and dependable measurements over sensors by closely regulating the synthesis conditions and ensuring consistent material properties. [36,37].

Shen et al. highlighted that MOFs are ideal candidates for the capture and sensing of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) due to their remarkable properties, such as high surface areas, exceptional chemical and thermal stability, and versatile host-guest interactions, which allow for adjustable porosity tailored to specific applications. [36]. Olorunyomi et al. further emphasized the wide array of application domains for MOFs, particularly in chemical sensing, where their flexibility in design and potential for functionalization play a crucial role. [37]. Given the growing demand for highly sensitive materials in chemical and biochemical sensing applications, such as environmental monitoring and personal diagnostics, MOFs have been recognized as sophisticated materials with great promise for integration into advanced analytical equipment. Recent research has shown the growing potential of MOF films in solid-state sensing technologies, employing various techniques, including electrical, electrochemical, electromechanical, and optical sensing. These studies underscore the suitability of MOFs for integration into optical and electrical analytical devices, offering new avenues for innovation. Moreover, the development of MOF-based wearables and smartphone sensors demonstrates early yet promising steps toward creating next-generation sensors for real-time monitoring, suggesting a future where such materials could be integral to the next wave of sensor technologies in diverse applications.

All the above properties and their significance is briefly detailed in Table 1, presented below.

The unique characteristics and practical applications of different MOFs in related domains are displayed in the Table 2.

3. MOFs synthesis techniques

These days, researchers have a unique platform for changing desirable features [45–49]. Over the last few years, various synthetic approaches have been used to produce new MOFs with different morphologies, high surface area, particle sizes, and pore sizes distribution. The synthesis process of MOFs is highlighted in the following subsections, emphasizing techniques such as solvothermal, microwave-assisted, and mechanochemical methods. These approaches allow the MOFs to be highly versatile for various applications, including gas storage, separation, and catalysis. The review also discusses

Table 1
Properties of MOF.

Property	Key Impact	Significance	References
Porosity	Enhanced sensitivity	The vast internal surface area of MOFs provides a large number of binding sites for analytes, increasing the probability of analyte-MOF interactions and leading to enhanced sensitivity.	[20]
Tunable pore size	Selective detection	MOFs can be synthesized with tunable pore sizes, allowing for the selective capture and interaction with specific analytes. This selective binding leads to enhanced selectivity.	[21,22]
Chemical tunability	Enhanced interaction and specificity	The chemical composition of MOFs can be modified by changing the organic linkers and metal nodes, which can alter the MOF's surface properties and bonding characteristics. This modulation of surface chemistry can enhance the interaction between the MOF and target analytes, leading to improved sensitivity and specificity.	[23,24]
Mechanical stability	Long-term performance under ambient conditions	MOFs typically exhibit good mechanical stability under ambient conditions, ensuring that they retain their sensing capabilities over extended periods. This stability is crucial for long-term deployments in real-world applications.	[26,28]
Biocompatibility	Safe integration into biomedical applications	MOFs used in biomedical applications must exhibit excellent biocompatibility, meaning they should not cause any toxic or harmful effects on biological systems. The use of non-toxic and biocompatible organic linkers is crucial for ensuring the safety of these sensors in biomedical settings.	[29,31–34]
Reproducibility	Consistent and reliable measurements	Reproducibility is crucial for MOF-based fiber optic sensors, as it ensures that sensors from different batches or prepared by different researchers provide accurate and reliable measurements. Careful control of MOF synthesis conditions and characterization of material properties are essential for achieving reproducible results.	[37]

advancements in scalable synthesis techniques aimed at improving the efficiency and environmental impact of MOF production. Table 2 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of MOF synthesis methods.

Table 2
MOFs with their special properties and their practical applications in relevant fields.

S. NO.	MOF materials	Properties	Practical Applications	Ref.
1.	ZIF-8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sodalite type structure Active under UV-visible illumination Bandgap = 4.9 eV 	Gas Storage, separation, catalysis and CO ₂ capture	[38]
2.	ZIF-67	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical stability Bandgap = 1.98 eV Visible light absorber Tunable pore size 	Energy storage, photocatalyst for the reduction of Cr(VI)	[38]
3.	HKUST-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermal stability Large porosity Large surface area Bandgap = 3.5 eV 	Remarkable gas separation and uptake, heterogeneous catalyst, sensing applications	[39]
4.	MIL-101	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigid architecture Higher hydrothermal and chemical stability Bandgap < 2.9 eV Mesoporous structure 	Drug delivery, sensing, membrane preparation, gas separation	[40]
5.	MIL-68 (Fe)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pseudo-semiconductor Bandgap = 2.8 eV Excellent stability 	Excellent photocatalyst for the reduction of aqueous contaminants, gas adsorption	[41]
6.	SCU-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ladder like structure Indirect bandgap = 2.48 eV Highly porous 	X-ray detection and imaging	[42]
7.	Ni-DABDT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conductive Electron transfer capability Higher stability 	Electrochemical applications, charge storage, X-ray detection,	[43]
8.	U10-66	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narrow bandgap High thermal stability, Superior chemical resistance 	Wastewater treatment applications	[44]

3.1. Hydrothermal / solvothermal method

The synthesis process entitled hydrothermal approach used a mixture of metal salts and organic ligands in a water (as a solvent) media to develop single crystal of MOFs. As the temperature of growth chamber varies, an autoclave—a steel pressure tank walled with teflon, utilised to supply nutrients through water to encourage crystal formation. [50]. Hydrothermal synthesis allows for compound crystallisation at high temperatures and vapour pressures. The solute sustenance dissolves at warmer side and deposits at cooler end, causing the formation of a single crystal. In this scenario, temperature of solvent rises above its boiling point and atmospheric pressure, but its dielectric constant and viscosity decrease, promoting an increased diffusion process that leads to crystal formation. This process usually carried out at temperatures below 200 °C and under pressure in an autoclave with teflon walls. It is also feasible to develop MOFs with high vapour pressure around their melting points via in situ ligand synthesis [51]. In contrast to zeolites, the bridging ligand exploited in the synthesis of MOFs is retained within the design during the whole process (Fig. 2 (a)) [52].

The solvothermal method is a widely used yet labor-intensive synthesis technique for producing MOFs, requiring fewer solvents while still yielding high-quality crystalline materials. Unlike the hydrothermal method, the solvothermal approach utilizes a non-aqueous precursor solution, which consists of organic ligands and isolated metal ions that cooperate to form the crystalline structures of the MOFs [50,53]. By

Fig. 2. MOF preparation and fabrication a) hydrothermal Synthesis of MOFs [52] copyright (2022) American Chemical Society; b) synthesis at room temperature [60] Copyright (2015) American Chemical Society; (c) ionothermal synthesis of MOFs [62] Copyright (2008), Elsevier; (d) microwave-assisted synthesis of MOFs [120] Copyright (2024), Elsevier; (e) electrochemical synthesis of MOFs [73] Copyright (2012), American Chemical Society; (f) mechanochemical synthesis of MOFs [80] Copyright (2024), Angewandte Chemie; (g) sonochemical synthesis of MOFs [89] Copyright (2024), Elsevier; (h) microfluidics-assisted synthesis of MOFs [92] Copyright (2024), Chemical Engineering Journal; (i) postsynthetic modification synthesis of MOFs [100] Copyright (2017), American Chemical Society.

carefully controlling factors such as temperature, solvent choice, precursor composition, and reaction time, this method combines the advantages of both hydrothermal and sol-gel techniques. This allows for precise control over the size, shape, and crystallinity of the resulting MOFs, offering the flexibility to tailor the material's properties for various applications. The synthesis parameters, including reaction time, temperature, stirring speed, and the metal/ligand ratio, play a significant role in determining the final shape and structure of the MOFs. For example, the solvothermal synthesis of zeolitic imidazolate frameworks such as ZIF-67 and ZIF-8 has been shown to yield promising results using specific solvents and reactants, but achieving optimal conditions requires extensive trial-and-error experimentation [54,55]. Despite its challenges, the solvothermal method offers considerable advantages by enabling the precise tuning of the materials' functionality, stability, surface area, and porosity, making MOFs suitable for a wide range of industrial applications [56]. Additionally, this method can be extended to the synthesis of other nanostructured materials, such as graphene, carbon, and titanium dioxide, further broadening its utility. Li et al. described the successful synthesis of LiFePO_4 using a hydrothermal/solvothermal approach, investigating the relationship between synthesis conditions and the nucleation and growth of LiFePO_4 [57]. The method allows for various modifications, including controlling particle size and orientation, adding electron-conducting layers, doping with aliovalent ions, and managing defects to improve the material's performance. These modifications are particularly valuable for enhancing the Li-ion diffusivity in LiFePO_4 , which is commonly used as a cathode material in Li-ion batteries. Similarly, Zheng et al. explored the synthesis of nickel-based MOFs (Ni-MOFs) through solvothermal methods, examining the effects of time and temperature on the morphology and electrochemical performance of the nanomaterials [58]. They conducted experiments at different temperatures, ranging from below the boiling

point of *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) to above the boiling point of ethylene glycol (EG). Their findings revealed that as the temperature increased, the average size of Ni-MOF nanosheets decreased, while the crystallinity of the MOFs improved. The synthesis time had only a minimal effect on the resulting nanostructures. Notably, Ni-MOF nanomaterials synthesized at 160 °C demonstrated excellent performance as symmetrical supercapacitor electrodes, achieving a high energy density of 22.44 Wh kg^{-1} and outstanding cyclic stability with a durability of 118 % over 10,000 cycles [58]. These findings highlight the potential of Ni-MOFs as promising candidates for use in energy storage devices, particularly in supercapacitor applications. Thus, solvothermal synthesis has proven to be a valuable method for developing MOFs and related nanomaterials with enhanced properties for a wide range of applications.

3.2. Synthesis at room temperature method

This procedure is part of an exclusive group of solvothermal techniques in which the reaction of organic ligands and isolated metal ions produces MOFs without any requirement of heating for synthesis or crystallisation process. For mild crystallisation of MOFs, the solvent utilised in the reaction mixture maintained at room temperature. As any base (like triethylamine) utilised during the reaction, the organic ligands get deprotonated and MOF precipitated from the mixture [59]. Due to its straightforward operation, high yield, and lack of additional energy requirements, this approach is typically chosen for the development of MOFs. This procedure is laborious, taking hours or even days, and some of the reactions need the use of acid modulators such as hydrofluoric acid and DMF, which is usually carried out under dangerous conditions (Fig. 2 (b)) [60].

Tovar et al. described a water-based synthesis method for producing

a wide range of CPO-27/MOF-74-M class MOFs, which included variants synthesized from Mg(II), Ni(II), Co(II), and Zn(II) ions [61]. This synthesis process, carried out at room temperature, involved optimizing several key reaction parameters, such as pH, reagent concentrations, and reaction time, to achieve the desired results. The optimization process was done in a step-by-step manner to ensure the best possible outcome. Through this approach, Tovar et al. successfully synthesized CPO-27-M MOFs with exceptional specific surface areas, achieving record-breaking BET surface areas of 1279 m²/g for CPO-27-Zn, 1351 m²/g for CPO-27-Ni, 1572 m²/g for CPO-27-Co, and 1603 m²/g for CPO-27-Mg. These surface areas are among the highest reported for this class of MOFs, demonstrating the method's effectiveness in producing highly porous materials. Additionally, the space-time yields (STYs) for these MOFs were also impressive, with CPO-27-Ni, -Mg, -Co, and -Zn achieving STYs of 44 kg/m³/day, 191 kg/m³/day, 1462 kg/m³/day, and a record-breaking 18720 kg/m³/day, respectively. These results highlight the potential of this synthesis method to efficiently produce MOFs with high surface areas and excellent yields, making it a promising technique for large-scale MOF production with various industrial applications.

3.3. Ionothermal method

Solvothermal synthesis has several limitations, including difficulties with inorganic precursor solubility and hydrogen bond interference when using water as a solvent. To overcome these issues, ionothermal synthesis has emerged as a competitive alternative. By employing a low-volatility ionic liquid as both the environmentally friendly solvent and the structure-directing agent, the ionothermal method effectively dissolves the precursors and encourages the synthesis of desirable MOFs with enhanced characteristics. For instance, with 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide ionic liquid as a solvent and trimesic acid, Xu et al. synthesized zinc trimesate ([Zn₄(BTC)₂(μ₄-O)(H₂O)₂]) via ionothermal method (Fig. 1(d)) [62]. Owing to their unique characteristics, which include low vapour pressure, high solubility for organic molecules, thermal stability, a wider liquid range, and nonflammability, ionic liquids hold promise as eco-friendly reagents for the synthesis of MOFs and other materials, including zeolites and chalcogenides (Fig. 2 (c)).

Wang et al. detailed the synthesis of Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks (ZIFs) of the sod (RCSR symbol) and zni (RCSR symbol) types through an ionothermal method, utilizing a urea-choline chloride deep eutectic solvent and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide ionic liquid [63]. This method involved a cooling-induced crystallization technique that played a significant role in determining the morphology of the final products. When the synthesis solution was rapidly cooled, the sod-type product exhibited a spherical shape, whereas the zni-type product exhibited rod-like or plate-like forms. This demonstrates how cooling rates and solvent choice can directly influence the structural characteristics of ZIFs, allowing for fine-tuning of their morphology for various applications. In a different study, Luo et al. developed a novel 3D MOF, denoted as (PMI)₂[Zn₄(μ₄-O)Br₂L₂], through ionothermal conditions involving tricarboxylic acid H₃L and Zn(NO₃)₂. The framework features a (3,6)-connected topological system and incorporates uncommon {Zn₄(μ₄-O)Br₂} clusters as fundamental building blocks. This new MOF, synthesized with the ionic liquid PMI (1-propyl-3-methylimidazolium), offers potential as a sensitive and recyclable luminous probe for detecting Fe³⁺ ions [64]. Furthermore, PMI has shown promise in absorbing cationic dyes efficiently and specifically, showcasing its potential for applications in environmental monitoring and wastewater treatment. These developments highlight the versatility of ionothermal synthesis in creating functionalized frameworks with unique properties for sensing and environmental applications.

3.4. Microwave synthesis method

Microwave (MW) illumination is a highly promising substitute for conventional methods in the production of MOFs. Its numerous

advantages led to its widespread application. As compared to traditional methods, this technology is more energy and time-efficient due to its rapid heating time, energy-saving procedure, higher yield, and high purity. The appropriate electromagnetic wave frequency can be employed to trigger molecules in a solution to collide, increasing the kinetic energy of molecules and raising the system's temperature [65]. Because of the radiation's immediate interaction with the solution, the heating process is more effective. Consequently, rapid crystallisation and a high nucleation rate are encouraged by microwave synthesis. Unlike traditional solvothermal methods, which need extended annealing times, microwave synthesis allows MOFs to be developed in a matter of minutes. Kim and colleagues, described a scalable method for MOFs synthesis with microwave volume heating in a continuous-flow tubular reactor (Fig. 2 (d)). With a space-time yield of up to ≈771.6 kg m⁻³ per day, the system successfully performed continuous crystallisation of MIL-100(Fe) under relatively mild circumstances (temperature: 100–110 °C, time: 50 min) [66]. Microwave heating and solvothermal techniques were used in a comparative study by Choi and colleagues to examine the structural and surface characteristics of MOF-5 [67]. After 30 min of microwave heating at various power levels, irradiation periods, temperatures, solvent concentrations, and substrate orientations, uniform cubic MOF-5 crystals with an average size of 20–25 μm and a surface area of 3008 m² g⁻¹ were obtained. In comparison, MOF-5 crystals with a size range of 400–500 μm and a surface area of 3200 m² g⁻¹ could only be synthesised via the traditional solvothermal process in 24 h at 105 °C. Ni and Masel successfully synthesized MOFs by microwave synthesis. Rather than the typical solvothermal synthesis requirements of 120 °C for 21 h, these MOFs were developed in a microwave synthesiser at 150 W for only 25 s [68]. The microwave method considerably assists in the large-scale production of MOFs and has an impact on the size and shape of the crystals. Bag et al. synthesised isostructural microporous lanthanide MOFs in around 5 min via MW-assisted solvothermal method [69]. In contrast, a lengthy 2 days reaction time and an additional 5-day evaporation interval were required for the solvothermal technique. Microwave-assisted synthesis has benefits beyond rapid crystallisation, including phase selectivity, particle size reduction, and morphological control. However, it does not have the massive crystal formation necessary to obtain high-quality structural data [70].

Ramu et al. outlined recent advancements in the fabrication of MOF thin films and membranes, particularly emphasizing the integration of microwave-assisted techniques, which have significantly improved the properties and functionalities of these materials, including their gas separation capabilities [71]. The production of high-quality MOF thin films and membranes has traditionally been challenging due to issues such as ensuring strong adhesion to porous substrates and managing the complexities of heterogeneous nucleation and growth. However, recent developments in microwave-based synthesis technologies have provided solutions to these challenges, enabling more efficient fabrication of MOF membranes with superior characteristics. Chen et al. further demonstrated the benefits of microwave synthesis in their work on MOF-(Ni) materials, which were engineered to feature numerous unsaturated metal sites and narrow micropore channels [72]. Their study showed that microwave-synthesized MOF-74 (Ni) exhibited an impressive CO₂ adsorption capacity of 5.22 mmol/g at 25 °C, which is roughly six times higher than the adsorption capacity of commercial activated carbon (0.89 mmol/g), and a CO₂/N₂ selectivity of ~ 31. Moreover, the MW-140 variant of the material displayed a high CO₂ adsorption capacity of 3.37 mmol/g even in humid conditions (RH = 90 %), underscoring its robustness under various environmental factors. The enhanced CO₂ capture performance was attributed to the combined effects of small micropore channels and the rich five-coordinated Ni²⁺ open metal sites within the MOF structure, which facilitated efficient CO₂ trapping and enhanced the material's overall gas separation properties [72]. These findings highlight the potential of microwave-assisted synthesis to produce MOF materials with optimized properties for applications such as

CO₂ capture, environmental protection, and energy storage.

3.5. Electrochemical method

In recent years, several innovative techniques have been developed for the fabrication of MOF thin films. Among these, the electrochemical method has emerged as the most favorable due to its simplicity, scalability, and ability to precisely control various factors, including phase, morphology, and thickness, through the adjustment of voltage during the deposition process. This method allows for the production of dense and homogeneous MOF thin films with minimal effort and equipment, making it an ideal choice for large-scale production. Electrochemical synthesis has gained particular popularity in the production of MOF films due to its mild preparation conditions, ease of control, and the potential for continuous, environmentally friendly large-scale manufacturing. The electrochemical method, which offers a rapid synthesis and mild reaction conditions, has been used to create MOFs. By using this technique, undesirable anions like nitrate, perchlorate, or halides are prevented from entering large-scale industrial operations. Metal ions are used in place of metal salts, and they are obtained as a metal source through anodic dissolution. The reaction mixture containing an electrolyte and an organic ligand is then supplemented with this highly reactive metal species through anodic dissolution. Protic solvents are frequently employed to prevent metals from depositing on the cathode, although this process produces H₂ (Fig. 2 (e)). The benefit of this technique is faster synthesis at lower temperatures without anionic residues [73]. The structure and shape of the produced MOFs are significantly influenced by the reaction time and the solvent content as well. If given enough time, a dense crystal layer may form partially, while the supporting mesh may suffer structural damage. Both solvent concentration and reaction duration have a significant impact on the structure and morphology of the generated MOFs. For example, the electrochemical method was perfect for developing HKUST-1 (CuBTC) due to its low temperatures (50 °C) and fast response times. The resultant crystal layers overcome the porous copper support [74]. Sachdeva et al. synthesised CuTATB (H₃TATB = 4,4',4''-s-triazine-2,4,6-triyl-tri-benzoic acid) as a bulk powder, which is another type of MOF [75]. The bulk powder exhibited needle-like characteristics and agglomerated particles with a BET surface area of 570 m² g⁻¹. When CuTATB grown on the copper surface, a rapid nucleation process leads to the development of smaller particles and inhibits interpenetration. Large-scale electrochemical apparatus and large-area metal electrodes make this process unsuitable for large-scale synthesis, and its low productivity is one of its main drawbacks [76].

Li et al. highlighted the growing significance of processable MOF films in a wide range of technologies, from advanced sensing devices to separation applications [77]. Ren et al. further discussed how this technique has paved the way for the development of novel MOFs, expanding their application in environmental analysis and offering more sustainable alternatives for practical use [78]. In one such example, Liu et al. utilized the electrochemical synthesis method to create large-area Cu₃(HHTP)₂ MOF sheets on a Cu (100) single-crystal anode [79]. This approach, driven by molecular assembly through charge-driven surface reactions, resulted in high-quality crystalline films with electrical conductivity of 0.087 S cm⁻¹. Remarkably, the size of the synthesized MOF films was about 1000 times larger than previously reported for the same material using other methods, such as the interface approach. This breakthrough has significant implications for enhancing the potential of MOF films in various industrial applications, particularly in the microelectronics sector, where large-scale, high-performance materials are crucial for future technological advancements.

3.6. Mechanochemical method

The development of MOFs using mechanochemical synthesis has significant potential to be beneficial for the environment and the

economy (Fig. 2 (f)) [80]. In this procedure, when the metal salts and organic ligands were crushed in a mechanical ball milling machine, the intermolecular linkages underwent mechanical breakdown, which was followed by chemical modification after creating new bonds. A highly crystalline, single-phase MOF with guest molecules in its spaces has been developed. The advantages of this method include a high yield of products at room temperature, safe byproduct production, fast reaction times, and the avoidance of solvents. However, to boost the reactants' molecular mobility, a minimum amount of solvents is added to promote mechanochemical reactions. Mesopores were observed to develop as a consequence of the remaining acetic acid molecules blocking the pores during the 25-minute reaction between trimesic acid and copper acetate, which developed HKUST-1. One post-synthesis activation was performed to eliminate the gaseous by-product, resulting in a high surface area of 1713 m² g⁻¹ [81]. This non-toxic technique is appealing because it can produce a range of MOFs at room temperature in a brief amount of time without requirement for solvents, high temperatures, or high pressure—all of which are necessary for the hydro/solvo thermal technique.

Xu et al. emphasized the significant potential of the mechanochemical method for the development of advanced catalytically active materials, attributing its popularity to several key advantages, such as its simplicity, high reproducibility, and ability to operate under mild and often solvent-free conditions, particularly through dry milling [82]. The approach not only offers a streamlined and environmentally friendly synthesis process but also enables the creation of high-performance catalysts with optimized properties. The impact of mechanochemical synthesis on the physicochemical characteristics and catalytic efficiency of MOF-based materials has been extensively examined [83]. This includes a detailed analysis of how mechanical energy, when applied during the synthesis, influences the formation of solid catalysts and their subsequent performance. Through careful design of metal-organic component combinations, this method enables the rational and precise construction of MOFs tailored to meet the specific demands of various applications, thereby enhancing their functionality. The mechanochemical approach is particularly advantageous when it comes to producing MOFs at the scale, purity, and cost necessary for commercial applications, allowing for their effective transition from laboratory-scale research to practical, large-scale technology. The method has already proven successful in a wide range of synthetic chemistry fields, contributing to the environmentally benign and efficient large-scale production of MOF materials. Miao et al. further explored the increasing interest in synthetic porous MOFs, particularly due to their versatile chemical characteristics, with a key application being their use in gas and vapor sorption processes [84]. MOFs are known to undergo reversible structural or phase changes in response to elastic deformation, which can affect their overall properties. However, when subjected to plastic deformation, the changes become more pronounced and permanent, altering the MOFs' crystal structure, pore size, and chemical bonding. These modifications can have a significant impact on their gas adsorption behavior, making them valuable in applications that require high levels of flexibility or adaptability. Notably, the high energies involved in the initiation of link rearrangements during plastic deformation position MOFs as promising candidates for shock wave attenuation applications, where the ability to absorb and dissipate energy is critical. This expanding knowledge of MOFs behavior under mechanical stress opens new pathways for designing advanced materials with specialized functions in energy management and environmental applications.

3.7. Sonochemical method

Another method for rapidly and sustainably synthesising MOF crystals is sonochemical synthesis, also known as ultrasound-assisted technique (20 kHz – 10 MHz). When compared to the solvothermal method, this technology can significantly shorten the crystallisation

period while also accelerating homogenous nucleation and the production of smaller particle sizes. The sonochemical production of a MOF $[Zn_3(BTC)_2]$ (BTC = benzene tricarboxylic acid) in ethanol was first reported by Qiu et al., they also investigated MOF's selective sensing towards organoamine [85]. Further, impact of reaction time on particle size of HKUST-1 was investigated using sonochemical method [86]. With this method, Son et al. succeeded to produce high-quality MOF-5 crystals with sizes ranging from 5 to 25 nm in about 30 min as opposed to 24 h via solvothermal approach [87]. Due to the short synthesis time and lack of requirements for an induction phase prior to sonicator stability, this method allows for minimal power usage and is less expensive than a microwave approach. In general, the nanocrystals are smaller relative to those generated via the solvothermal technique. Instead of incorporating DMF in the solvothermal synthesis, 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), an affordable solvent, can be employed to produce MOFs on a wide scale. Khan and Jung discovered that the rates of crystallisation and crystal growth during the synthesis of MIL-53 using solvothermal, ultrasonic, and microwave procedures were found to be in the following order: ultrasound (US) > microwave (MW) > solvothermal (ST) [88]. Recently, Yao et al. synthesised ZIF-8, ZIF-67, and Co/ZIF-8 with meticulously planned particle sizes and morphologies using a mild and effective ultrasound-assisted synthesis technique (Fig. 2 (g)). By varying the amount of cobalt doped into the heterometallic ZIF-8 structure, a tunable particle size ranging from 35 nm to over 300 nm was obtained [89]. This process's low product yield and restricted heating depth make it difficult to use for the large-scale synthesis of MOFs [76].

Jung et al. explored the structural characteristics and CO₂ adsorption properties of MOF-177, synthesized through a sonochemical process, which incorporates Zn₄O clusters and 4,4,0,4'-benzene-1,3,5-triyl-tri-benzoate (BTB) linkers [90]. The synthesized MOF-177 exhibited impressive surface area and porosity, with a specific surface area (SSA) of 4898 m²/g and a total pore volume (V_t) of 2.3 cm³/g. Additionally, the CO₂ adsorption capacity of MOF-177 was notably high, reaching 29.89 mmol/g at 30 bar and 25 °C, when synthesized under optimal sonochemical conditions—specifically, 40 min of sonication at 60 % power (maximum 500 W at 20 kHz). This enhanced performance highlights the significant influence of the sonochemical method on the material's structural properties and gas adsorption capabilities.

Similarly, Yu et al. utilized a sonochemical approach to synthesize Zr-based porphyrinic MOFs, MOF-525 and MOF-545, both containing Zr₆(OH)₄O₄(CO₂)₁₂ and Zr₆O₈(CO₂)₈(H₂O)₈ clusters, respectively [91]. For MOF-525, the procedure involved the ultrasonic treatment of zirconyl chloride octahydrate and benzoic acid in dimethylformamide for 30 min, followed by the addition of tetrakis(4-carboxyphenyl)porphyrin (TCPP) and a subsequent sonochemical treatment. After sonicating the solution for three hours at 30 % power (102.2 °C), MOF-525 was synthesized with a high SSA of 2557 m²/g, a pore volume of 1.26 cm³/g, and cubic/needle-shaped crystals with particle sizes ranging from 0.5 to 5 μm. For MOF-545, sonication was performed at 60 % power (118.2 °C) for 30 min, followed by acid washing, resulting in a material with an SSA of 2248 m²/g and a pore volume of 1.77 cm³/g. MOF-545 exhibited needle-shaped crystals with particle sizes between 0.8 and 1.2 μm. The increased SSA, pore volume, and the presence of defects in both MOFs contributed to improved performance in adsorption and catalytic applications. For example, MOF-545 demonstrated an excellent adsorption capacity of 492.4 mg/g for bisphenol-A, highlighting the material's potential for environmental and industrial applications [91]. These findings emphasize how the sonochemical method, by enhancing the surface area and creating defect sites, can significantly improve the performance of MOFs in various applications, including gas storage, separation, and catalytic processes.

3.8. Microfluidics method

Controlling the various aspects of MOF synthesis is essential to

ensure the desired properties and functionalities of the material. In this context, the microfluidics technique has emerged as a promising solution, advancing the field of MOF synthesis by enabling continuous production and precise control over reaction parameters. This technique significantly enhances the scalability, versatility, and efficiency of MOF manufacturing, allowing for more reproducible and tailored outcomes. Microfluidics is a technique for chemical synthesis that controls fluid flows at the micro- and nanoscale. By controlling precise synthesis settings, this technique enables the continuous manufacturing of MOFs, hence advancing the usage of MOFs in terms of intensification, variety, and scalability (Fig. 2 (h)) [92]. This method can be applied to the synthesis of various MOFs, such as those based on imidazolates (ZIF-7 and its variants) and carboxylates (HKUST-1, Cu-BTC, MOF-5, IRMOF-3, UiO-66) [92]. Mao et al. demonstrated the automated and integrated data storage of DNA within MOFs in a short period of 10 and 5 min, respectively [93]. DNA is an exceptional data storage platform. DNA microlibrary@MOFs had improved stability as well as quick data retrieval capabilities after deteriorating. While the synthesis on a microfluidic chip takes around a minute, the synthesis of MOFs using a traditional solvothermal technique takes 72 h. Numerous benefits of using microfluidic-assisted synthesis include the ability to manipulate morphological features, fine-grained particle size, high repeatability, and the absence of huge work areas and costly equipment. Compared to traditional methods, this approach also provides the prospect of defect-free MOF-based hollow fibre membranes that save reactants. Even if this method surpassed others in a number of ways, there are certain problems when creating MOFs at high temperatures [94]. Echaide-Górriz highlighted the numerous advantages of integrating microfluidics with MOF synthesis, not only facilitating the fabrication of MOFs with well-defined hierarchical structures but also enabling the production of hollow fiber membranes, which are particularly useful in separation technologies. These membranes can offer improved performance in various applications, such as gas separation and filtration [95]. Koryakina et al. further emphasized the potential of microfluidic methods to overcome critical challenges encountered in conventional nanomaterial synthesis, particularly in achieving a high rate of heat and mass transfer, and precise control over synthesis conditions [96]. Such capabilities make microfluidics an ideal approach for producing MOFs with consistent and reproducible physicochemical properties. The controlled environment offered by microfluidics can ensure the uniformity and quality of synthesized materials, which is difficult to achieve using traditional synthesis methods. Moreover, microfluidics enables the efficient manipulation of small volumes, reducing the cost and time required for experiments and allowing for high-throughput screening of different MOF structures and functionalities. Recent advancements in microfluidics have also found applications in the synthesis of optically responsive nanomaterials, such as plasmonic, photoluminescent, and shape-changing nanoparticles. Liu et al. explored the use of microfluidics in drug development, where the technique is revolutionizing the process by providing a highly controlled and compact environment for biochemical reactions [97]. In comparison to traditional drug development methods, which can be time-consuming and labor-intensive, microfluidics allows for faster, more efficient processes in drug synthesis, delivery, and evaluation [97]. By facilitating precise manipulation of chemical reactions, microfluidics has the potential to greatly accelerate the discovery and development of new therapeutic compounds, demonstrating its broad applicability beyond material science. Overall, the integration of microfluidics into MOF synthesis and drug development paves the way for more efficient, scalable, and controlled production processes, with promising implications for a wide range of industries.

3.9. Postsynthetic modification (PSM) method

Post-synthetic modification (PSM) techniques have proven to be highly effective for introducing new functionalities into pre-existing

MOFs, significantly enhancing their versatility and expanding their potential applications. According to Lin et al., the PSM process for functionalizing MOFs can be categorized into four primary strategies: encapsulation, hybridization with other molecules, covalent modification, and coordinative transformation [98]. These methods are instrumental in altering the structural and chemical properties of MOFs, enabling the incorporation of specific features that may not be present in the original framework. By modifying the framework after its synthesis, PSM techniques provide a versatile tool for tailoring MOFs to meet the specific demands of various applications, such as improving their structural stability, enhancing reactivity, or enabling selective functionality. These innovations have substantially broadened the scope of MOFs, making them applicable to a wide range of industries, from environmental protection to energy conversion. Furthermore, Lin et al. explored the development of functionalized MOFs for photocatalytic applications, including water splitting, CO₂ reduction, organic transformations, and the degradation of water pollutants [98]. These modifications improve the catalytic efficiency and selectivity of MOFs, making them more suitable for sustainable energy production and environmental remediation. Research into PSM has led to significant advancements in the properties and performance of MOFs, particularly for energy and environmental applications. As the demand for more efficient materials grows, PSM techniques allow for the fine-tuning of MOFs to meet the specific requirements of emerging technologies, such as renewable energy generation and carbon capture. The rapidly expanding field of MOF research has also contributed to the diversification of applications, as noted by Baa et al., who observed that the wide range of potential uses, including gas sorption, energy storage, catalysis, and biological applications, has accelerated the development of these materials [99]. They also discussed the evolving synthesis methods and how they contribute to the increasing relevance of MOFs in diverse fields, from environmental sciences to biomedicine. These advancements have positioned MOFs as a key material in the development of next-generation technologies, showcasing their adaptability and broad potential. Through continued innovation and refinement of post-synthetic modification techniques, MOFs are likely to play an increasingly significant role in solving critical challenges in energy, environment, and health sectors. In order to increase the range and adaptability of functional groups integrated into primary MOFs, postsynthetic modification, or PSM, has gained widespread acceptance (Fig. 2 (i)) [100]. Cohen explained the idea of “postsynthetic modification” and conducted organic reactions on MOFs utilising the PSM technique via single or multistep reactions to create topologically identical but functionally diverse MOFs [101]. Multiple PSM approaches on metal exchange, ligand exchange, guest replacement, and metalation of open coordinate sites in ligands may be created, which can work independently or in concert, to fabricate various functional groups incorporating MOFs [102]. Bennet observed that the amine group in ZIF MOFs is in charge of lowering the melting temperature as well as enabling the PSM approach to adjust the surface’s characteristics from hydrophilic to hydrophobic in the presence of octyl isocyanate [103]. This method is an effective way to create new MOFs in mild reaction circumstances since it is highly orientated, versatile, and easy to manage, and it can produce heterogeneous metal–organic frameworks with little interference. This method’s shortcomings include the formation of new intracrystalline or intercrystalline flaws as well as the degradation of crystallinity [104]. The potential for porosity control and extensive synthesis with PSM method have been a driving force behind this investigation. It also demonstrated promise as viable options for biological applications, including drug delivery, bioMOFs, sensing, and imaging, among other areas. Even though these materials are still a long way from achieving commercial success, their demonstrated capabilities in sensing, drug administration, and imaging have elevated them to the status of promising prospects for a biological revolution [99].

The ability to control porosity and the versatility of the post-synthetic modification (PSM) method have been key factors propelling

the ongoing research and development of MOFs. These capabilities have opened up new avenues for tailoring the properties of MOFs to meet the specific needs of various applications. Notably, the PSM approach has shown significant promise in advancing the use of MOFs in biological applications such as drug delivery, biosensing, and medical imaging, among other biomedical fields. The ability to precisely engineer the structure and functionality of MOFs makes them highly attractive for designing materials that can interact with biological systems in a controlled and efficient manner.

Although these materials are still in the early stages of development and far from reaching commercial viability, the progress made so far highlights their considerable potential. In particular, MOFs have demonstrated impressive capabilities in the targeted delivery of drugs, real-time sensing of biological markers, and enhanced imaging techniques, all of which could revolutionize medical diagnostics and treatment strategies. Their unique properties, such as high surface area, tunable pore sizes, and the ability to encapsulate bioactive molecules, provide a foundation for developing more effective and personalized therapies. As research advances, it is anticipated that these materials will undergo further refinement, bringing them closer to widespread use in clinical and pharmaceutical applications.

In summary, while the journey toward commercial success remains a challenge, the demonstrated capabilities of MOFs in biological fields have raised their profile as highly promising candidates for revolutionizing medical applications. Their potential to significantly improve drug delivery systems, diagnostic imaging, and biosensing devices positions them as a key focus of ongoing biomedical research. With continued advancements in synthesis methods and PSM techniques, MOFs may eventually play a pivotal role in shaping the future of healthcare and biotechnology.

Table 3 explained the advantages and disadvantages of different synthesis methods of MOFs.

4. Sensing Mechanisms

There are several sensing mechanism which are exploited for the sensing of various entities using the MOF materials and its integration with the fiber optic, as described in the following subsections.

4.1. Refractive index (RI) modulation

RI modulation-based MOF-based fiber optic sensors (FOSSs) are among the most widely investigated types of MOF-based sensors due to their simplicity, versatility, and high sensitivity. These sensors typically employ a MOF-coated fiber optic probe that is immersed in a sample solution containing the target analyte. When the analyte binds to the MOF, it alters the RI of the solution, which in turn affects the RI of the light traveling through the fiber optic cable. This RI change can be detected using various optical techniques, including spectrophotometry, interferometry, and waveguide dispersion analysis. Kim et al. illustrated an effective strategy and the exceptional performance of optical gas sensors based on nanoporous MOF securely affixed to the surface of an etched optical fiber [121]. This design facilitated the detection of a broad spectrum of small molecules by leveraging minimal differences in refractive indices, linked to analyte adsorption within the MOF structure. The resulting sensors exhibited remarkable selectivity to CO₂ gas in comparison to other small gases (H₂, N₂, O₂, and CO) with improved sensitivity, rapid response times (<tens of seconds) and excellent reversibility, attributes well-associated with the physisorption of gases into the nanoporous MOF [121].

4.1.1. FO-SPR model for Full-Spectrum signal analysis of back-reflecting FO-SPR sensors to monitor MOF deposition

Vandezande et al. explained the complete spectrum capabilities of fiber-optic surface plasmon resonance (FO-SPR) for further analysis of heterogeneous samples. Their model incorporates significant changes to

Table 3
Advantages and disadvantages of various synthesis methods for MOF synthesis.

S. No.	Synthesis methods	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
1	Hydrothermal	Low cost; Produce large, high quality crystals; Control over composition; Homogeneous precipitation; Easy to scale up; Environment friendly.	High vapour pressure; Produce liquid waste; Low yield.	[52,78]
2	Solvothermal	Precise control over the size, morphology, and crystallinity of particles; High yield under milder conditions; Clean reaction; Produce a wide range of nanoparticles with a narrow size distribution; Can synthesize MOFs with two different metals.	Long reaction time; Requires high temperature; Require more solvent; Produce unwanted by-products.	[105,106]
3	Synthesis at room temperature	Inexpensive; Rapid process; High quality crystalline; Novel and environment friendly.	Low bulk density; High pressure drop which makes them difficult to implement in industrial fields; Limited versatility.	[76,107]
4	Ionothermal	User-friendly; Time-efficient; Minimal use of solvent; Ionic liquids can be reused.	Limited to low-melting metal salts	[108,109]
5	Microwave	Fast crystallization; Increased productivity; Reduced particle size; Selective phase formation; Morphology control; Environment friendly.	Solvent stability; MOFs Stability; Reaction time scale.	[76,110]
6	Electrochemical	Mild reaction conditions; Shorter reaction times; Crystallized structures free of metal salts; Less energy consumption;	Not used widely Costly	[111,112]
7	Mechanochemical	Clean reaction; Fast in speed; Simple than conventional routes.	Long processing time; Contamination; Uncontrollable particle microstructure; Agglomeration.	[113,114]
8	Sonochemical	High yield; Short reaction	Limited versatility;	[115,116]

Table 3 (continued)

S. No.	Synthesis methods	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
		time; Smaller particle size; Phase selectivity; Cost effective; Minimal energy used; Ease synthesis.	Size and morphology control; Complex reactions; Limited scalability.	
9	Microfluidics	Precise control; Cost-effective; Rapid synthesis; Improved process safety; Improved heat and mass transfer; Reduced byproduct formation.	Clogging; Scaling up production; Small amounts of product; Less flexible for multiphase systems.	[117,118]
10	Postsynthetic modification	High stability; High functionality; High processability; High conductivity; High hydrophobicity; High chirality; High yields; Facile purification	Scaling; Toxic; Database of clinical trials High cost.	[102,119]

the angular dispersion of light within the system as well as modifications to the thickness and permittivity of the gold SPR-active layer on the FO-SPR sensor. With the assistance of FO-SPR, they use this optimised model to examine the deposition process of a metal-organic framework (MOF), in the instance of ZIF-8. They propose a dual-parameter analysis by simultaneously determining the evolving thickness and refractive index (RI) of the MOF layer by attentively examining the temporal fluctuations in the FO-SPR signal during MOF layer development. It demonstrated that samples displaying radial heterogeneity may provide valuable information from a full-spectrum analysis of the FO-SPR signal. This development greatly improves the quantitative evaluation of a number of phenomena, including adsorption and binding activities, that modify the refractive index throughout the sensor's area. As a consequence, it is a significant advancement in FO-SPR sensor technology, with potential for wide-ranging applications in domains requiring for the accurate detection and analysis of complicated materials. The full-spectrum analysis of the deposition of a ZIF-8 MOF layer onto a back-reflecting FO-SPR sensor was successfully conducted using a unique FO-SPR model. The model made it possible to calculate layer thickness and RI precisely. The measurable ranges for thickness and RI were determined to be 19–582 nm and 1.3727—1.4596, respectively (Fig. 3) [122].

Schematic overview of the back-reflecting FO-SPR probe and its multilayer structure is provided, highlighting the critical parameters that influence the FO-SPR signal. The thicknesses of the recognition and gold layers are denoted as d_r and d_{Au} , respectively. The evanescent wave intensity, indicated by EW, is most pronounced near the interface between the gold and recognition layers due to the SPR phenomenon. The relative permittivities of the sample (s), recognition layer (r), gold (Au), and glass (g) are indicated by ϵ_k . The FO-SPR probe has a diameter (D) and length (L). The reflection angle of the incident light ray in the FO-SPR denoted as α .

It can be divided into three subsections:

4.1.1.1. *Fiber optic interferometry.* Optical interferometers are widely

Fig. 3. An outline of the multilayer structure and back-reflecting FO-SPR probe, emphasising the key parameters influencing the FO-SPR signal. Where, d_r and d_{Au} represent the thicknesses of the gold and recognition layers, respectively. Because of this SPR phenomena, the evanescent wave intensity, or EW, strongest in the vicinity of the interface between the gold and recognition layers. The relative permittivities of the glass (g), gold (Au), recognition layer (r), and sample (s) are denoted by ϵ_k . The diameter (D) and length (L) of the FO-SPR probe are known. α represents the incident light ray's reflection angle in the FO-SPR [122]. Copyright (2024) American Chemical Society.

recognized for their exceptional precision in measuring small changes in the optical path difference (OPD), which can be caused by variations in physical movement, temperature, pressure, or changes in refractive index within the interferometer system. The basic operation of an interferometer involves splitting an incoming light beam into two separate components: a reference beam and a sensing beam. These beams travel through different optical paths, and once they are recombined, they generate an interference pattern that contains valuable information about the measured variable [123,124]. In an interference pattern, constructive interference occurs when the OPD corresponds to an even number of half wavelengths, while destructive interference occurs when the OPD corresponds to an odd number of half wavelengths. These optical paths may be associated with separate optical fibres or may be contained within a single optical fibre that supports multiple modes [124]. For high-precision measurements, interferometers commonly use light sources with high coherence, such as lasers, because the coherence length of the light must be greater than the OPD to maintain a stable and clear interference pattern. In the field of environmental monitoring, interferometric systems have been applied to detect contaminants in water. For instance, Nazari et al. developed an optical fibre sensor system based on a metal-organic framework (MOF) thin film, specifically UiO-66, for detecting water pollution [125]. This sensor was designed for use at the tip of a single-mode optical fibre (SMF-28), providing a simple and scalable solution. The sensor was utilized to detect rhodamine-B and methyl viologen in a mixed aqueous solution. The Fabry-Perot interferometry technique served as the core of the optical detection system, enabling the analysis of interference signals. The fast Fourier transform (FFT) method was employed to process

the data, clearly illustrating that the interaction of the two pollutants in the water resulted in complex physical and chemical phenomena that could be distinguished based on specific frequencies associated with each analyte. This approach demonstrated the potential of using MOF-based optical fibre sensors for real-time environmental monitoring with high sensitivity and accuracy.

4.1.1.2. Long period grating (LPG) / Long period fiber grating (LPFG). Long period fibre gratings (LPFGs) are a crucial part of the optical fibre sensor family, drawing significant attention for their exceptional capabilities and unique advantages. Unlike conventional fibre gratings that reflect light back, LPFGs are transmission-based, meaning they do not cause back-reflection and thus do not require isolation in the sensing system. This feature enhances their functionality in various applications. LPFGs are particularly valued for their high sensitivity to changes in temperature, strain, transverse load, and refractive index, making them useful for precise measurements in diverse fields. The operation of LPFGs involves coupling light from a guided mode into forward-propagating cladding modes through the grating. This interaction results in light being scattered and absorbed as it propagates. The coupling between the guided mode and cladding modes is dependent on the wavelength, and the strength of this coupling leads to spectrally selective loss, which is a key characteristic of LPFGs. Essentially, the grating periodically modulates the optical fibre's characteristics, enabling the interaction of multiple copropagating modes, a feature that differentiates LPFGs from fibre Bragg gratings (FBGs). Due to their periodic structure, LPFGs can operate at wavelengths significantly longer than the radiation traveling through the fibre, a feature that allows them to surpass the limitations typically imposed by the fibre's geometry and material properties. LPFGs are relatively simple to fabricate because their period is much larger than the wavelength of the light they interact with. Since LPFGs couple copropagating modes, the resonant wavelengths manifest as dips in the transmission spectrum, which corresponds to the cladding modes. This provides a clear method to observe their resonance behavior, particularly in a single-mode fibre where the transmission spectrum reveals the wavelengths associated with different cladding mode resonances [126]. In a notable application, Hromadka et al. developed an optical fibre-based volatile organic compound (VOC) sensor using a functional coating of ZIF-8, a member of the zeolite imidazolate framework (ZIF) family. ZIF-8 was applied to the LPFG surface through an in-situ crystallization process, involving a combination of zinc nitrate hexahydrate and 2-methyl-imidazole in methanol. This functionalized LPFG sensor was highly responsive to various VOCs, such as acetone, ethanol, and methanol vapours, especially in high concentration ranges, reaching up to tens of thousands of parts per million. The sensor demonstrated optimal performance at the phase-matching turning point (PMTTP), where the resonance condition for light coupling is most sensitive to the presence of VOCs. A novel data analysis method, based on measuring the bandwidth of the LPG's U-shaped attenuation band, was also developed to improve sensor performance. The sensor's limit of detection (LOD) was found to be 5.56 ppm for ethanol and 6.67 ppm for acetone, with sensitivities of 0.015 ± 0.001 and 0.018 ± 0.0015 nm/ppm, respectively [127]. This combination of high sensitivity and selective response makes LPFG-based sensors highly promising for VOC detection in environmental and industrial monitoring applications.

4.1.1.3. Transmission spectroscopy. The development of novel chemical sensing platforms can be significantly enhanced by integrating optical fibres with sensitive thin films, offering a versatile approach for detecting various analytes. Kim et al. introduced a simple yet highly effective design for nanoporous metal-organic framework (MOF)-based optical gas sensors, which can detect a wide range of small molecule concentrations with exceptional performance [121]. The sensing mechanism relies on detecting minute changes in refractive indices,

which occur as a result of analyte adsorption within the MOF structure. This approach amplifies the intrinsic optical absorption properties of the MOF layer, allowing for precise detection of gas adsorption through the effective refractive index values. Similarly, Burck et al. developed a fibre optic chemical sensor aimed at identifying organic molecules in aqueous solutions, using an innovative in-situ measuring probe based on the evanescent field principle [128]. This sensor utilizes a quartz glass fibre coated with polysiloxane, which plays a dual role: protecting the fragile silica fibre core and providing selectivity for non-polar organic molecules due to the organophilic nature of the siloxane coating. The sensor takes advantage of the interactions between the evanescent field at the interface of the core and the cladding, enabling the detection of organic species that penetrate the cladding without interference from large water absorption bands in the near-infrared (NIR) region. The system employs a commercially available fast-scanning dispersive NIR spectrometer linked to a small sensor comprising a 6-meter coiled fibre. The NIR absorbance spectra of chlorinated hydrocarbon solvents (CHS) such as methylene chloride, chloroform, and trichloroethylene were measured in the 900–2100 nm spectral range, showing the characteristic absorption bands of these solvents diffusing into the fibre cladding. Quantitative measurements were taken using aqueous solutions of chloroform (CHCl₃), with concentrations ranging from 80 to 6800 mg/l. A clear linear relationship between absorbance and concentration was established, demonstrating the sensor's effectiveness. In kinetic tests, the sensor response times for CHCl₃ solutions ranged between 5 and 10 min, showcasing the system's efficiency and reliability for chemical sensing applications.

4.2. Fluorescence enhancement

Fluorescence enhancement is another promising sensing mechanism for MOF-based FOSs, offering enhanced sensitivity and selectivity for a variety of analytes. This technique involves functionalizing the MOF with fluorescent molecules that can either be quenched or enhanced by the interaction with the target analyte [129–131]. Portable sensing devices and high-sensitivity oxygen probes are in high demand due to their wide range of applications in fields such as environmental monitoring, healthcare, and industrial processes. Lanthanide-based metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), with their inherent porosity and remarkable lanthanide luminescent properties, have garnered significant attention for their ability to provide highly sensitive oxygen (O₂) sensing. These MOFs offer a promising solution due to their exceptional sensitivity to changes in oxygen levels, making them ideal candidates for real-time and portable monitoring systems. Optical fibre sensors, in particular, have proven to be an effective and straightforward platform for this type of detection, offering advantages such as ease of integration, portability, and the ability to operate in challenging environments. In this context, Xia et al. developed an oxygen-sensitive porous lanthanide MOF, EuNDC (where 1,4-H₂NDC refers to 1,4-naphthalenedicarboxylic acid), which exhibited remarkable performance in oxygen detection [132]. Compared to other lanthanide-based MOFs, EuNDC demonstrated superior characteristics, including short response time (~ 10 s) and recovery time (70 s), making it highly suitable for real-time sensing applications. The material also displayed impressive sensitivity, with a 93.5 % quenching at 1 bar O₂, and a high quenching efficiency ratio (I₀/I₁₀₀ = 15.4), indicating its ability to effectively detect even small changes in oxygen concentration. Furthermore, its sensitivity constant (KSV) of 13.3 bar⁻¹ and a low limit of detection (LOD) of 0.21 mbar demonstrate the material's outstanding capability to detect minute oxygen levels with high precision. The reversibility of the sensor also adds to its practical utility, ensuring that it can be used repeatedly without significant degradation in performance, making it an ideal candidate for portable, high-sensitivity oxygen sensing applications.

4.3. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR)

SPR-based MOF-based FOSs are particularly attractive for high-sensitivity and real-time sensing applications. These sensors utilize the SPR phenomenon, where light interacts with a metal layer deposited on the fiber optic waveguide. When the light is of a specific wavelength, it excites surface plasmons, collective oscillations of electrons on the metal surface.

The SPR angle, representing the specific angle of incidence where surface plasmon resonance is induced, can be precisely monitored by detecting variations in the refractive index of the medium in direct contact with the metal surface. This change in refractive index corresponds to alterations in the surrounding environment, allowing for high sensitivity to even minute changes. Zheng et al. developed a reflective optical sensor utilizing SPR to measure glucose concentrations [133]. In their system, the sensor detects shifts in the SPR angle as a result of the interaction between the glucose molecules and the sensor's surface, providing a reliable method for continuous, real-time glucose monitoring. The gold film was sputtered onto the surface of a plastic-clad optical fiber to induce SPR and facilitate light reflection simultaneously. This configuration enabled the SPR sensor to exhibit heightened sensitivity to even small changes in the surrounding refractive index. To enable glucose detection, glucose oxidase (GOD) was chosen as the sensing layer due to its specific enzymatic activity, and it was covalently bonded to the gold surface. Upon exposure to glucose, the enzyme catalyzed a reaction that altered the local refractive index around the sensor. This change in the refractive index caused a detectable shift in the SPR spectrum, which could be directly correlated with the glucose concentration. By continuously monitoring the resonance wavelength shift, the glucose levels in the sample could be quantified in real-time.

Liu et al. designed a fiber-optic localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) sensor with a specialized tip for the detection of acetone. This sensor utilizes gold nanoparticles, approximately 40 nm in size, attached to the tip of a multi-mode optical fiber for chemisorption purposes [134]. The sensor's functionality is further enhanced by layer-by-layer functionalization with a metal-organic framework (MOF), specifically HKUST-1. This design aims to leverage the unique properties of both the gold nanoparticles and the MOF, providing an effective platform for detecting acetone vapors. The researchers explored two different sensors, each with a varying number of MOF layers—80 and 120—resulting in different film thicknesses that directly impacted the sensor's response. The interaction between acetone molecules and the HKUST-1 thin film causes a change in the local refractive index, leading to a measurable shift in the resonance wavelength of the LSPR sensor. As acetone is adsorbed into the MOF film, a redshift in the resonance wavelength is observed, allowing the sensor to detect the presence of acetone. The response of the sensors is highly sensitive to acetone concentration: as the concentration increases, the sensors approach saturation, and when the acetone concentration decreases, the shift is completely reversible, demonstrating the sensor's dynamic range and responsiveness. Notably, the sensor with the thicker film, consisting of 120 layers, exhibited a slightly higher sensitivity to acetone, showing a wavelength shift of 5.27 nm at a 3.4 % acetone concentration. This suggests that increasing the film thickness enhances the sensor's ability to detect acetone, highlighting the importance of optimizing the number of layers for achieving improved performance in gas sensing applications.

4.4. Electrochemical detection

Electrochemical sensing is a method for converting electrochemical information into readable signals by the use of electrical potentials and currents, which are typically measured as a function of the electrochemical reaction. There is an electrochemical reaction that occurs between an analyte and a metal-organic framework (MOF) when the target analyte binds to the MOF material and initiates an

electrochemical reaction as a result. In general, the function of this mechanism is to identify and quantify the target element that attaches to the electrode, which is its primary purpose. Upon interaction with various analytes such as heavy metal ions, organic pollutants, glucose, amino acids, DNA, or uric acid, the MOFs selectively adsorb these compounds. In response to this adsorption, the concentration of the target analyte on the electrode surface increases, allowing the system to detect changes in the electrical signal. The presence and concentration of the analyte is measured by an electrode placed near the MOF-coated fiber optic probe [135].

4.5. Thermometric sensing

An analyte binds to a MOF in thermometric sensing, which measures the change in temperature. An analyte that is present in MOFs will alter its structural properties, causing the material to exhibit expanding, contracting, or phase transitions, thereby altering its optical, electrical, and magnetic properties, as well as its optical, electrical, and magnetic properties. These physical changes will be accompanied by changes in the material's properties that will influence its performance. There can be a detectable shift in temperature as a result of these structural changes in the MOF. In order to measure these changes in temperature, a thermocouple or thermistor is typically embedded within the fiber optic probe that has been coated with MOF, so that the variation in temperature caused by the interaction between the analyte and the MOF can be detected with high accuracy. There are a number of applications in which thermometric sensing can be used to detect and quantify analytes that trigger significant temperature-related responses upon binding, which can lead to highly sensitive detection in a wide range of analytical disciplines [136].

5. MOF based fiber optic sensor

5.1. MOF coated fiber optics chemical sensor

In recent years, MOFs have shown potential applications in sensing,

especially since they can be incorporated with fibers for selective sensing applications of gases, chemicals, and biomolecules. Menon et al. recently studied detection of Chromium ion, Cr(VI) using a reproducible and scalable coating of metal organic framework, ZIF-67 on optical fiber (Fig. 4) [137]. ZIF-67 matrix selectively entraps Cr(VI) ions, and the U-FOS probe's high evanescent wave absorption (EWA) sensitivity allows specific detection of Cr(VI) ions via their intrinsic optical absorption at 395 nm. As compared to other potential heavy metals and interfering metal ions present in water, the developed sensor shows high selectivity for detecting chromium ions, such as Mn(VII), Fe(III), Co(II), Na(I), Cu(II), Cr(III), Pb(II), Hg(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), and Li(I). Using a compact LEDOPD setup, the FOS/ZIF-67 chromium sensor demonstrates a wide dynamic range, short response times, and useful detection limits down to 1 ppb [137].

The FOS/ZIF-67 probes were evaluated for Cr(VI) detection and quantification using halogen light sources and fiber optic spectrometers. Various concentrations of aqueous Cr(VI) ions (0, 100, 500, 1 k, 10 k, and 50 k ppb) were applied to the U-bent sensing region. The EWA spectra recorded for each concentration of Cr(VI) using fresh FOS/ZIF-67 probes, shown in Fig. 5(a), revealed an absorbance peak at 395 nm, corresponding to the characteristic absorption of Cr(VI) (which appears yellow to the naked eye). A proportional increase in peak absorption at 395 nm was observed as Cr(VI) concentration increased, driven by refractive index changes caused by the binding of Cr(VI) to the ZIF-67 matrix. Compared to Cr(VI) in solution at 368 nm, the bound Cr(VI) on the U-FOS probe exhibited a notable redshift in the absorption wavelength. This shift from 368 nm to 387 nm, observed in solution phase studies of Cr(VI) and Cr(VI) + ZIF-67, is attributed to the adsorption of Cr(VI) on the ZIF-67 layer. The additional shift to 395 nm observed in the FOS/ZIF-67 probe is likely due to further adsorption of Cr(VI) ions on the ZIF-67 film surface. SEM micrographs of the Cr(VI)-treated probe surface (Fig. 5(b)) reveal significant morphological changes in the ZIF-67 layer, supporting the observed redshift. Moreover, elemental composition analysis via EDAX confirms the presence of Cr in the ZIF-67 matrix after exposure to 50 ppm of Cr(VI) ions [137].

A selectivity test was performed after successful Cr(VI) detection

Fig. 4. (a) The detailed step-by-step process for developing the proposed FOS/ZIF-67 sensor probe. (b) The absorbance spectral response of the FOS/ZIF-67 sensor probe to 1 ppm of Cr(VI). (c) The sensing mechanism illustrating the potential chemical interactions between Cr(VI) and the ZIF-67 immobilized on the fiber probe surface, along with the corresponding SEM micrographs [137]. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society.

Fig. 5. (a) Spectral response of FOS/ZIF-67 based on EWA for various concentrations of Cr(VI) in DI water. (b) SEM images of Cr(VI)-treated FOS/ZIF-67 at magnifications of 10 \times and 50 \times (inset) [137]. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society.

with FOS/ZIF-67 probes by testing the probe with different heavy metals that may interfere with Cr (VI) in real samples. During this study, the interfering in concentration was chosen as 50 ppm, which is 50 times higher than the Cr (VI) concentration (1 ppm) (Fig. 6). In contrast to Cr (VI), none of the heavy metal ions showed an absorbance response at 395 nm except for Mn(VII), Fe(III), Co(II), Cu(II), and Cr(III) at 13, 8, 4, 3, and 2.5 % respectively [137]. Table 4 showed configuration of few chemical sensors with target analyte and their detection limit including their advantages / disadvantages.

5.1.1. Ethanol sensor based on cascaded tapered optical fiber with surface modification of ZIF-8

Wang et al. discussed a cascade tapered optical fibre sensor with surface modified ZIF-8, to detect traces of ethanol in the air at room temperature [144]. With an in-situ growing approach, ZIF-8 was mounted on the surface of the detecting tapered optical fiber. Concurrently, a Vernier effect was created by connecting tapered fibre in series with similar free spectral ranges (FSRs), which can magnify small variations in the detecting tapered fiber's surface refractive index (RI) (Fig. 7). The RI sensitivity of single tapered fiber was 9.6 times smaller than that of cascade tapered fibre, at 18,366.17 nm/RIU. The sensitivity was 0.1411 nm/ppm in the concentration range of 0–140 ppm. The stability and reversibility of the sensor were verified by the adsorption and desorption tests carried out with different concentrations of ethanol vapour. It performs quickly and effectively with response and recovery times of 8 and 12 s, respectively, for 25 ppm ethanol gas. The sensor's selectivity is demonstrated when testing several volatile organic compounds (VOC) gases; it responds more strongly to ethanol vapour. Additionally, even in difficult settings, real-time monitoring of the concentration of ethanol vapour, made possible by incorporated sensor. The sensor also useful instrument for tracking ethanol leaks in industrial production because of its high sensitivity, good reversibility, and

constant detection ability.

5.1.2. Ultrafast response optical microfiber interferometric VOC sensor based on evanescent field Interaction with ZIF-8/Graphene oxide Nanocoating

A potential way to improve photonic sensing is to incorporate nanomaterials into photonic devices to improve light-matter interaction. To build evanescent field-based photonic devices, nanomaterial interaction with photonic devices should be explored. Huang et al. developed multilayer ZIF-8 nanomaterials on graphene oxide (GO) premodified optical fiber to examine the light-matter interaction between nanomaterials and photonic devices (Fig. 8) [145]. The incorporation of GO effectively improves ZIF-8's weak adherence on the optical microfiber, facilitating the synthesis of a very homogeneous morphology. Through experimentation and simulation, the optical properties of ZIF-8 are obtained based on the change in the evanescent field that occurs throughout the growing phase of ZIF-8 on the optical microfiber. The sensing platform's functionality tested with ethanol, and a concentration-specific response observed that corresponds to the theoretical conclusions, with a high sensor response at ambient temperature and a low limit detection of 5.26 ppm. Due to its porous nature and large specific surface area, the GO/ZIF-8 multilayer fiber sensor provides an ultrafast sensor response (118 ms), demonstrating potential for industrial and environmental applications. Concentration-specific responses to ethanol and methanol vapours with a dynamic range up to ~ 6850 ppm were obtained by detecting variations in transmission spectra due by chemical molecule infiltration into ZIF-8 pores. The RI of ZIF-8 film is around 1.40.

5.1.3. Detection of volatile organic compounds using surface plasmon Polaritons and Ultra-Thin Metal-Organic framework films

MOFs are a promising material to realise chemical sensors because of

Fig. 6. (a) Selectivity and (b) interference evaluation of FOS/ZIF-67 probes with different metal ions [Mn(VII), Fe(III), Co(II), Na(I), Cu(II), Cr(III), Pb(II), Hg(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Li(I)] in DI water (number of probes, n = 3) using the experimental setup [137]. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society.

Table 4
Chemical sensor configuration and their detection limit.

S. No.	Advantages/Disadvantages	Target analyte	Sensor configurations	Concentration range	Detection limit	Sensitivity	References
1	Highly sensitive	Chromium ion	Solution-phase/MOR-2/UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectrometer	5–50 ppb	4 ppb	50 ppb	[138]
2	Very low detection limit	Chromium ion	Straight optical fiber/Ag nanoparticles/Methimazole/Raman spectrometer	0.005–500	0.005 ppb	1×10^{-11} M	[139]
3	Short response time	Chromium ion	Straight optical fiber with fiber Bragg grating/hydrogel/interrogator	10–100 ppb	10 ppb	1.2 pm/ppb	[140]
4	Highly selective fast response time and low detection limit	Chromium ion	Straight optical fiber/ag-ITO/hydrogel	1×10^{-11} to 10×10^{-3} M	0.5×10^{-11} M	6.67×10^{10} nm M ⁻¹	[141]
5	Short response time (~5–10 min) and low detection limit	Chromium ion	U-bent optical fiber/ZIF-67/Photodetector	1 ppb	5–100,000 ppb	5.9 ΔA/RIU	[137]
6	Highly selective and fast response time	Iron ion	Straight optical fiber/quantum doped hydrogel	0.5–4 μM	0.5 μM	–	[142]
7	Selective detection and response time of 5 min	Hg ²⁺	D-shaped optical fiber/paste of Al ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles	2–20 ppm	4 ppm	–	[143]

Fig. 7. Set up a tapered optical fibre gas sensor [144]. Copyright 2024, Elsevier.

their guest adsorption capabilities. But in order to achieve high sensitivities, well-defined MOF films must be deposited consistently and integrated with an appropriate sensor design. The technique of effectively detecting volatile organic compounds (VOCs) by converting the adsorption in chemical vapour deposition (MOF-CVD)-prepared zeolitic imidazolate framework 8 (ZIF-8) thin films into surface plasmon polariton (SPP) shifts that can be detected via total internal reflection ellipsometry (TIRE). It is demonstrated that the VOC uptake is altered by defect creation during MOF-CVD. On the contrary, under ideal synthesis circumstances, SPP resonances as sharp as 14 nm and adjustable over the entire Vis – NIR range can be obtained. When methanol is absorbed, record-breaking changes more than 150 nm and a detection limit of less than 1 ppm are observed. Changes in ZIF-8 refractive index from 1×10^{-4} (single-digit ppm VOC concentration) up to 0.06 are resolved with a resolution greater than 1×10^{-5} via modelling the TIRE spectra. Fig. 9(a) exhibited the arrangement of the TIRE sample. Ag/oxide/MOF layered samples deposited on a glass substrate. Ag(55 nm)/AlO_x(10 nm)/MOF stacks optically modelled in order to show the SPP shift depending on MOF layer thickness. The TIRE spectra of bare Ag sheets reveal peaks at 370 nm (FWHM = 16.4 nm). The SPP shifted slightly beyond 400 nm by adding 10 nm AlO_x (Fig. 9(b)). MOF applied at a wavelength of 20–200 nm results in SPP peak locations ranging from 464–935 nm, with FWHMs of 7.5–9.2 nm. The effect of k on the SPP peak gets displayed in Fig. 9(c) since MOF materials may not be perfectly transparent ($k > 0$) and may even experience spectral absorption (colour) shifts upon the adsorption or desorption of guest molecules. An increase in k from 0 to 0.1 broadens the SPP FWHM to nearly 40 nm without changing its position, as demonstrated for a 100 nm MOF film (Fig. 9(c)) [146].

5.1.4. Ethanol sensor based on No-Core fiber coated with Metal-Organic framework

The combination of functionalised nanofilms and optical fibre represents an intriguing potential for the development of extremely sensitive sensors. Lu et al. explained a highly sensitive liquid sensor for

ethanol based on porous MOF nanofilms coated no-core fibre (NCF) [147]. The normal sensor node (NSN) structure made up of one single mode fibre (SMF) segment and two NCF segments. Low concentration ethanol aqueous solution can be detected because interaction of initial concentration effect in porous zeolitic imidazolate framework (ZIF-8) and multimode interferences (MMIs) effect in NCF. Compact ZIF-8 nanofilms uniformly generated on the surface of NCFs via in situ crystallization technology, and NSN sensing structure consists of two cascade MMIs. Due to NCF coreless structure, which increases the evanescent wave proportion of power, the MMI effect in NCFs was extremely sensitive to the refractive index of its surroundings. Additionally, the ethanol molecules possess the ability to be adsorbed and concentrate in ZIF-8 nanofilms, which causes an amplification of the fluctuations in refractive index. The proposed sensor had high volume fraction and ethanol/aqueous solution limit of detection (LOD) of 0.90 % and a high sensitivity of 1.522 nm^{-1} (Fig. 10).

5.1.5. Detection of volatile organic compounds using a Metal-Organic framework modified Open-Cavity optical fiber Fabry-Pérot interferometer

Volatile organic compound (VOC) detection is essential for public safety, environmental monitoring, and industrial production. VOC sensors must possess inherent safety, considering the flammability and toxicity of typical volatile organic compounds. Researchers provide fibre optic sensors a lot of attention because they provide a versatile and passive method for detecting volatile organic compounds. Wang et al. develop an open-cavity optical fiber Fabry-Perot interferometer (FPI) with a fibre patch cable and a 3D-printed structural component with ZIF-8, on a side-polished silicon wafer (Fig. 11) [148]. Experimental research conducted on the sensing performance for common VOCs, such as methylbenzene, methanol, and ethanol. The results show sensitivities of 0.118p.m./ppm, 0.177p.m./ppm, and 0.412p.m./ppm, respectively. At the molecular level, sensitivity differences are analysed and demonstrated. The suggested technologies provide an alternative for the detection of VOCs in industrial production because of their simple manufacturing, intrinsic safety, compact size, and strong selectivity.

5.2. MOF coated fiber optics gas sensor

Environmental and industrial application of sensitive and selective sensors to detect hazardous gases is becoming more and more important and is also becoming increasingly interesting subject for research. Due to their excellent sorption kinetics, reversibility, and guest-induced changes to the MOF structure and/or properties, nanoporous materials such as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have gained increased interest in the fabrication of chemical sensors in recent years. In optical devices, MOFs can adsorb guest molecules, allowing measurements of optical properties. As a result of the presence of gas molecules in the pores of MOFs, their effective refractive index (RI) should be sensitive.

Fig. 8. (a) Spectrum of the input light and (c) spectrum of the output light; schematic diagram of (b) the fabrication process and (d) the fabricated microfiber; (e) simulated fiber mode power normalized to input power during the coupling–beating–coupling process; (f) calculated intensity of light propagation through the nonadiabatic biconical microfiber; (g) schematic diagram illustrating the modification step at the interface of the optical microfiber; (h) schematic of the final ZIF-8/GO-functionalized sensor. The enlarged view shows the interaction between the evanescent field and MOF/GO. (i) optical photograph of the actual functionalized microfiber [145]. Copyright 2021, John Wiley and Sons.

Direct RI-based gas detection by Fabry-Perot-based high-resolution spectroscopy has been achieved, but there are few reports of MOF-based optical devices that are capable of sensing gases by modifying their RIs as gases are absorbed. They are only developed for relatively large RIs changes due to adsorption of large molecules, such as hydrocarbons, alcohol, and water. As a result, this sensing technique has been less successful when applied to small molecules (e.g. H_2 , N_2 , O_2 , CO, and CO_2). This is due to their extremely small differences in RIs, which results in a lack of significant progress and success. It is necessary to explore new types of sensing and measurement systems that provide a highly sensitive, selective, and stable response to target gases in order to overcome the limitations of relatively weak RI responses for small molecules in order to further develop an array of MOF-based optical sensing applications.

Using zeolitic imidazole framework (ZIF)-8 MOF, Kim et al were able to fabricate fiber optic probes that are chemically/thermally stable and have reasonably high hydrophobicity (Fig. 12) [121].

An illustration of the gas sensing system designed in this study and the MOF-coated optical fiber sensor is shown in Fig. 13 (a). With an increasing number of deposition cycles, FE-SEM images were used to

investigate the morphological features and growth kinetics of ZIF-8 thin films on optic fibers. A cross-sectional image (Fig. 13 (c)) and a top-view (Fig. 13 (b)) of ZIF-8-coated optical fiber demonstrate extremely uniform, dense, and continuous ZIF-8 film coating, which is crucial to high-performance sensing. As the deposition cycle increased, the MOF film thickness on the optical fiber increased proportionally by 75 nm per cycle [121].

Researchers studied the sensing performance of 350 nm ZIF-8 coated fiber sensors to a wide range of gases with extremely similar RIs. The gas mixtures (50 v/v% of H_2 , CO, O_2 , and N_2), or single gases (100 v/v% of H_2 , CO, O_2 , and CO_2) were sequentially switched to N_2 to represent the base signal. In comparison, no reaction was observed for bare etched fibers. N_2 has very small RI differences compared to other gases (H_2 , O_2 , CO, and CO_2), and small molecule gases do not absorb light in the visible and UV ranges. The ZIF-8 coated optical fiber sensor exhibits highly sensitive/selective responses to CO_2 gas only, while H_2 , CO, and O_2 gases show negligible responses (Fig. 13). Based on the ratio of %T (100 % CO_2) and %T (50 % CO_2/N_2), it appears that the sensing response is proportional to gas amount physically adsorbing on the sensing layer and its effective real index. In addition, the CO_2/N_2 sensing showed

Fig. 9. The TIRE/SPP concept. (a) the sample layer stack and measurement geometry of TIRE; (b) simulated SPP spectra for Ag(55 nm)/AlOx(10 nm)/MOF stacks with MOF layers ranging in thickness from 20 to 200 nm; (c) Modelled broadening of SPP resulting from a 100 nm MOF layer when the MOF k -value increases from 0 to 0.1 [146]. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society.

almost the same response compared to the mixed gases, suggesting that the other gases do not affect CO₂ sensing selectivity and paving a way for industrial application of such MOF-based optical sensors.

The UV–Vis absorption spectra (Fig. 14) is shown for Cu-BTC (MOF) coated fiber [149].

A UV–vis–NIR spectrometer was used to study the optical properties of MOF thin films. A Cu-BTC MOF film growing on a 300 μm sapphire substrate was measured for absorbance, as shown in Fig. 15. In the crystal structure of Cu-BTC MOF, a d-d band absorption peak was observed around 700 nm, which is related to the typical copper carboxylate complex absorption at 1565–1585 nm [149]. Fig. 15 illustrates how UV–vis–NIR spectrometers measure absorbance. Since MOF layer has a highly rough surface, the small portion of “Absorbance” that decreases monotonically with wavelength is scattering.

To obtain the absorption spectrum for the MOF-coated single-mode fiber (SMF) sensor, an amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) light source and an oxidized sodium alginate (OSA) were used. To remove all gas molecules from the sensor, especially water vapor inside the porous structures, the sensor was purged with pure Ar gas for 12 h prior to the measurement. A reference spectrum was then collected based on the transmission spectrum. A switch was then made from pure Ar to pure CO₂. As soon as the transmission spectrum stabilized, it was collected. Based on Beer-Lambert law, the absorption spectrum is shown in Fig. 15 (a). In addition to gas phase CO₂ absorption, the absorption spectrum in a quartz gas cell (PIKE Technologies Inc. 162–1810) (Fig. 15 (b)) was also recorded. The rotational fine lines of gas phase CO₂ matched both the theoretical and experimental results from HITRAN database. Unlike gas phase CO₂, however, CO₂ sorbed MOF films exhibit a broad absorption peak between 1568 and 1572 nm. Due to the bonding effect of gas molecules inside the MOF pores, the missing rotational fine lines of the absorption spectrum were attributed to the energy transition change of rotational states. There is also a possibility that the discrepancy between these two spectra is due to the interaction between CO₂ molecules and MOF sorption sites. Moreover, since these multiple peaks are repeatable in the experiments, they must be the other vibrational band between 1576 nm and 1588 nm. It is also possible that the bonding state affected the vibrational band symmetry. Table 5 showed the various gas sensors with their target gas and their detection limit.

Fig. 10. The experimental configuration for the detection of ethanol solutions.

Fig. 11. The introduction of organic volatile substances into the ZIF-8 film lengthens the FP cavity's effective optical path, which causes the FP cavity's spectrum to shift. The amount of absorbed organic volatile components is positively associated with the spectral offset [148]. Copyright (2025), Elsevier.

Fig. 12. (a) Schematic illustration of the gas sensing system and optical fiber sensor integrated with a MOF thin film. (b) Top view and (c) cross-sectional FE-SEM images of a 200 nm ZIF-8 coated optical fiber, showing the uniform and continuous thin film [121]. Copyright (2018), American Chemical Society.

5.2.1. Fabry-Perot cavity utilizing metal-organic framework/graphene oxide heterostructure membranes for humidity sensing

Zhang et al. explained a Fabry-Perot (F-P) cavity with high-performance relative humidity (RH) sensing, which composed of heterostructure membranes consisting of graphene oxide (GO) and metal-organic framework 801 (MOF-801) [156]. To obtain the ideal reflection waveform, the MOF-801 concentration, spin coating period, and spin coating speed are adjusted to optimise the cavity reflectance spectrum. The humidity sensing capabilities of the MOF-801 membrane and MOF-801/GO heterostructure membrane F-P cavities were examined systematically. In comparison to MOF-801 membranes, MOF-801/GO heterostructure membranes exhibit lower detection limit (0.31 % RH) and higher humidity sensitivity (0.32 nm / % RH) due to the multifunctional reactive groups of GO ability to interact with H₂O, hence adsorption of H₂O enhanced. At 90 % relative humidity, the MOF-801/GO heterostructure membrane F-P cavity exhibited a maximum

response value of 27.9 nm ($\Delta\lambda$) and a quick optical response (400 ms). Additionally, there is high selectivity for H₂O vapour among the four interfering gases (CO₂, N₂, He, and Ar) in the MOF-801/GO heterostructure membrane cavity. Even with varying RH levels, the cavity maintained remarkable repeatability and dependability. The MOF-801/GO heterostructure membrane F-P cavity exhibited outstanding sensitivity when breathing through the mouth, demonstrating that the cavity is an effective choice for respiratory monitoring in humans. The F-P cavity, which based on MOF-801/GO heterostructure membranes, enable a way to develop humidity sensors that can detect humidity levels in real time with great performance (Fig. 16) [156].

5.2.2. A miniature optical Fabry-Perot interferometer based on a single-crystal metal-organic framework for the detection and quantification of low concentrations of benzene and ethanol in nitrogen gas

A miniaturised Fabry-Perot interferometer (FPI) combined with MOFs was used for the first time by Mumtaz et. al., to detect ultralow-concentration of chemical gases in real-time utilising fiber-optic technology. The sensor's tiny single crystal of HKUST-1 MOF, which imparts chemo-selectivity properties, contained in a short, thick-walled silica capillary segment that spliced to a lead-in single-mode fibre (SMF) and detection was based on the changes in FPI interference signal due to ethanol and benzene. A sensitivity of 0.428 nm/ppm between 24.9 and 40.11 ppm for ethanol gas concentrations and 0.15 nm/ppm between 99 and 124 ppm for benzene gas concentrations, was reported. Three ultralow concentrations of ethanol, benzene, and toluene gases were used in the selectivity study. The results showed an enhancement factor of 140 % for toluene and 436 % for benzene, which was explained by the conjugated ring molecules' improved miscibility with the alkane chains of the ethanol-modified HKUST-1. Experimental testing validated the feasibility of the sensor, exhibiting markedly enhanced response time and spectral features via crystal polishing, indicating its potential for ultralow concentration chemical gas detection and quantification. This device may prevent energy resource losses, and the sensor's small size and robust design make it usable in tight and dangerous locations. A schematic layout of the experimental setup, that included a static optical interrogator with a frequency scan rate of 2 Hz and a scanning wavelength range of 1510–1590 nm, showed in Fig. 17. This configuration was employed to collect the sensor spectrum [157].

5.2.3. Optical microfiber coated with a Ni-MOF-74 film for CO gas detection

Carbon monoxide (CO) can be effectively preserved with MOF materials. With a composite optical fibre structure built on tapered microfiber (TMF) and spiral fibre grating (SFG), this assembly can sense temperature and CO concentration simultaneously by spanning various

Fig. 13. The transmission spectra of (a) 350 nm ZIF-8 and (b) 160 nm Co/ZIF-8 coated optical fibers after exposure to varying concentrations of CO_2 . Absorption spectra of 2-mlm, ZIF-8, and Co/ZIF-8 were recorded from samples diluted in methanol, respectively. (c) Optical response of the 350 nm ZIF-8 coated optical fiber sensor to different pure gases. (d) Dynamic response at ~ 242 nm of the 350 nm ZIF-8 coated optical fiber after exposure to various gases or gas mixtures, as indicated. All sensing tests were conducted at room temperature and 1 bar without pretreatments, with N_2 used as the reference and/or carrier gas [121]. Copyright (2018), American Chemical Society.

functional films. CO molecules can be absorbed by Ni-MOF-74 deposited on tapered microfiber to alter its refractive index (RI). The spiral fibre grating period will alter according to the ultraviolet (UV) glue's thermal expansion. Based on the aforementioned process, it demonstrates the optical microfiber has a temperature sensitivity of $-30.1 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and a CO sensitivity of 64.11 pm/ppm . Since the spiral fibre grating contained a temperature sensitivity of up to $294 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, it can effectively offset the microfiber's temperature sensitivity. The precise monitoring of CO gas content is one area in which this composite structure has promising application prospects. Fig. 18 depicted the stages involved in preparing the two optical fibre configurations. The initial step often used piece of equipment for producing optical fibre devices is the optical fibre taper machine. It can be used to create a spiral grating preparation system in addition to drawing an optical fibre taper. Fig. 18(a) illustrated the replacement of the optical fibre taper machine's fastening device with an automated twisting device. Both the propulsion engine and the twisting device are activated upon preheating the optical fibre. It's possible to alter the SFG's period by adjusting the motor and translation stage speeds. According to Fig. 18(b) and 18(c), the spiral structure coated with a silver mirror reaction, with the film thickness regulated at $1 \mu\text{m}$, to prevent excessive light loss. Lastly, to improve the temperature sensitivity of SFG, UV glue (CV3003 SIRNICE) with a high coefficient of thermal expansion used for the packing structure. After the silver film

coated, the SFG inserted into a unique cylinder-shaped tube, and the UV glue injected gradually (Fig. 18 (d)). According to Fig. 18(e), the structure immediately exposed to UV radiation to sterilise it. According to Fig. 18 (f) and 18 (g), adjacent SFG regions for tapering in order to create a microfiber. To encourage the formation of MOF film on its surface, submerge TMF in the prepared mother liquor for two days, as indicated in Fig. 18(h) [158] After the sample dried for a day at room temperature and rinsed with tetrahydrofuran solution. It used in fabrication of dual parameter optical fibre sensors structure. The components of the optical fibre sensing structure are TMF and SFG. Ni-MOF-74 has an extremely robust metal skeleton and capable of efficiently adsorbing CO molecules. Thus, here a good chance that, this composite structure and new materials will be used to measure gas concentrations accurately.

5.2.4. Ultra-sensitive NIR fiber-optic gas sensors coated with Metal-Organic framework (MOF) for CO_2 detection

This study explores the use of MOFs in combination with fiber-optic technology for highly sensitive CO_2 detection in the near-infrared (NIR) range. The MOF coatings on the fiber-optic sensors enhance the interaction between the gas molecules and the sensor, resulting in improved detection limits. This innovative approach shows promise for applications in environmental monitoring and industrial safety. Although

Fig. 14. The absorbance spectrum of a 100 nm thick Cu-BTC MOF film deposited on a sapphire substrate [149]. Copyright (2016), Elsevier.

substantial improvements in terms of portability and cost, near-infrared (NIR) gas sensing still remains a huge difficulty due to its comparatively weak overtone absorption from the fundamental vibrational bond absorption at the mid-IR frequency. Chong et al. developed ultra-sensitive NIR gas sensing for carbon dioxide (CO₂) at 1.57 μm wavelength with a single-mode optical fibre coated with nanoporous Cu-BTC (BTC = benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylate) MOF [159] Without observing any side bands

Fig. 15. The absorption spectra of (a) CO₂ confined within the MOF and (b) CO₂ in the gas phase within a quartz gas cell [149]. Copyright (2016), Elsevier.

Table 5

Configuration of gas sensors with target gas and their detection limit.

S. No.	Advantages/Disadvantages	Target gas	Sensor configurations	Concentration range	Sensitivity	Detection limit	References
1	Highly selective and sensitive	Ammonia gas	Straight optical fiber/Gold-PMMA-reduced graphene coating	10–100 ppm	0.9 nm/ppm	10 ppm	[150]
2	High sensitivity, and selective	Hydrogen gas	Straight optical fiber/ITO thin films-ITO nanoparticles coating	10 ppm-100 ppm	0.071 nm/ppm	10 ppm	[151]
3	Selective detection	Carbon dioxide gas	Straight optical fiber/MOF coating	Volume percentage	–	–	[121]
4	Excellent Sensitivity and low detection limit	Hydrogen gas	Straight optical fiber/Gold-MOF coating	Volume percentage	–	–	[152]
5	Selective detection but Poor Sensitivity	Carbon mono oxide gas	Straight optical fiber (nano core)/Co/Ni-MOF	0 ppm to 35 ppm	0.0006 nm/ppm	1 ppm	[153]
6	Excellent sensitivity and Selective detection	Nitrogen dioxide	D-shaped straight fiber/D plasmonic tungsten oxide	44 ppb to 700 ppb	0.006 μW/ppb	8 ppb	[154]
7	Poor selectivity	Organic gases	Long period grating fiber/MOF coating	0 ppm-9000 ppm	–	–	[155]

associated with rotation, they were able to acquire high-resolution NIR spectroscopy of CO₂ absorbed in MOF, that closely packed gas molecules within the MOF pores did not free to rotate. The complicated sorption mechanism of CO₂ in Cu-BTC MOF, responsible for the varying response times observed in real-time measurements of the mixed gas flow of CO₂ and Ar based on CO₂ concentration (Fig. 19). Most significantly, here, they also explain ultra-low CO₂ detection limit (< 20 ppm) with a Cu-BTC MOF thin film, which was coated on 5 cm long single-mode optical fibres. Fig. 19 depicts the CO₂ sensing experimental setup. The light source (Thorlabs, Inc. S5FC1550S-A2) and a tunable semiconductor laser diode (HP 8168) were utilised to couple light into the fiber-optic sensor through fusion splicing another SMF with the gas sensor. When fusion splicing was used instead of optical coupling with 3-axis stages, the coupling stability was increased by 20 dB, which increased the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The CO₂ and Ar gases were connected to a gas cell that housed the gas sensor. A power metre (Thorlabs, Inc. S122C) or an optical spectrum analyser (Thorlabs, Inc. OSA203) was directly connected to the transmitted light through the sensor, and a personal computer was used to gather the data. Mass flow controllers (MFC) (Aalborg, GFC 17) with a flow range of 0–20 mL min⁻¹ were used to regulate the gas flow rates. By altering the CO₂ and Ar flows' mixing ratio, different CO₂ concentrations might be reached.

5.2.5. Metal-organic framework thin films on a surface of optical fibre long period grating for gas sensing

An optical fiber long period grating (LPG) coated with 40 layers of HKUST-1, a metal-organic framework (MOF), used to detect carbon dioxide (CO₂). The sensing mechanism involves measuring changes in the refractive index (RI) of the coating, which occur as CO₂ molecules enter the HKUST-1 pores. The study investigates the response of the resonance bands in the transmission spectrum of the LPG sensor when exposed to CO₂ mixed with nitrogen. Hromadka et al. developed a

Fig. 16. (a) Development of MOF-801 nanoparticles; (b) development of F-P Cavity; (c) schematic diagram of sensing device [156]. Copyright (2024), American Chemical Society.

Fig. 17. The experimental sensing setup used to detect varying amounts of gas-phase guests adsorbed in a single crystal of HKUST-1 MOF is shown in the schematic diagram. The sensor was placed inside a small gas chamber connected to the Owlstone system, where N₂ gas was used for purging, and the Owlstone gas generator controlled the guest concentrations. Real-time data were captured using an SMF-125 interrogator, which was operated through a laptop computer [157]. Copyright (2024), American Chemical Society.

carbon dioxide (CO₂) sensor based on optical fibre long period gratings (LPG) coated with HKUST-1 (HKUST-1). The deposition feasibility (time and cost efficiency) and CO₂ sensitivity of the film evaluated between in-situ crystallisation and layer-by-layer (LbL) methods of HKUST-1 thin film synthesis. The measurement of the coating change in refractive index (RI), which brought by CO₂ molecules seeping into the HKUST-1 pores, basis for the sensing process. Using ellipsometry, the thickness and refractive index (RI) of the thick films with 10, 20, and 40 layers

were ascertained. The films' crystallinity was assessed with X-ray diffraction pattern (XRD). When exposed to CO₂ in the range of 500 ppm to 40,000 ppm, an LPG modified with 10, 20, and 40 layers of HKUST-1 films using LbL method demonstrated good sensitivity. However the sensor coated using the in-situ crystallisation process showed no reaction to CO₂. When the fibre placed inside a closed polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) box of 15 x 15 x 15 cm, the reaction of the LPG was examined. Five centimetres above the chamber floor, the LPG was fixed

Fig. 18. A schematic illustration of the optical fibre sensor structure fabrication technique. (a) device for automatically twisting; (b) silver mirror reaction technique; (c) SFG after implementing silver film; (d) used UV glue procedure; (e) treatment procedure of UV glue; (f) procedure for fibre tapering; (g) structure of optical fiber composite; (h) growth procedures for MOF films; (i) diagrammatic representation of composite optical fibre [158]. Copyright (2024), Elsevier.

Fig. 19. The schematic diagram depicts the experimental setup for CO₂ sensing, where ASE represents Amplified Spontaneous Emission, OSA stands for Optical Spectrum Analyzer, and MFC denotes Mass Flow Controller [159]. Copyright 2016, Elsevier.

(Fig. 19). With a detection limit of 401 ppm, the film with 40 layers showed the maximum sensitivity to CO₂ [160].

An array consisting LPG1 and LPG2, with respective periods of 109.5 and 110.5 μm , had been developed, and LPG1 subsequent to being coated with 40 layers of HKUST-1. By analysing fluctuations in the central wavelength difference linked to the attenuation bands of bare and coated LPGs, the array's efficacy as a CO₂ sensor was assessed. When

subtracting the effects of temperature and other environmental perturbations (such as the flow effect of gas that might contribute to the LPG's relaxation), the bare LPG serves as an indicator. Fig. 20 illustrates the transmission spectrum of the array obtained in the air prior to and following the deposition of HKUST-1 on LPG1. Fig. 21 demonstrated that the attenuation band corresponding to LPG1 shifted as a result of the HKUST-1 film being deposited, while the attenuation band corresponding to LPG2 stayed in place [160].

5.2.6. Detection of alcohol vapors via metal organic framework functionalized surface plasmon resonance sensors

ZIF-8 and ZIF-93 MOFs are grown on fiber optic surface plasmon resonance (FO-SPR) sensors to detect volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in gases (Fig. 22). These coatings were applied via sequential nucleation and growth phases, with their kinetics monitored by FO-SPR. To achieve a sequential nucleation and growth phase, ZIF-8 and ZIF-93 were homogeneously functionalised with FO-SPR probes in each case using two distinct precursor solutions. The FO-SPR system instantly observed the variations in MOF nucleation and growth kinetics of the two solutions. In order to determine the two established MOF-FO-SPR sensors' sensing capabilities, these were then put through a series of sensing experiments using various alcohol vapours. Vandezande et al. successfully detected the vapours at mPa partial pressures and ppm concentrations with limit of detection (LOD) of 2.5 ppm for methanol [161]. It is possible to obtain qualitative information about the composition of the vapour by utilising the distinction in recognition behaviour between the more hydrophilic ZIF-93 recognition layer and the hydrophobic ZIF-8 recognition layer.

Fig. 20. A schematic illustration of the CO₂ sensitivity experiment setup. First, nitrogen poured into the chamber, and subsequently, the CO₂ content rises. A spectrophotometer used to measure the amount of light that transmitted through the fibre when the LPG optical fibre sensor is inserted into the chamber [160]. Copyright (2018), Elsevier.

Fig. 21. Transmission spectrum of Array A exhibited attenuation band of LPG1 (in the inset, black and blue, respectively), before and after 40 layers of HKUST-1 deposited over LPG1 [160]. Copyright (2018), Elsevier. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 22. Diagrammatic illustration of a MOF-FO-SPR probe which was not expanded [161]. Copyright (2017), American Chemical Society.

5.2.7. Fiber optic methane sensors with metal–organic framework functionalized polymer coatings

An interesting strategy to create inexpensive point and distributed fibre sensors for large-scale applications is the integration of functional polymer coating with optical fibre. In order to monitor natural gas infrastructure, Cao et al. described the creation of gas-sensitive coatings for single-mode and multi-mode optical fibres using polymer/nano-crystalline metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) composites as methane sensors (Fig. 23) [26]. For the well-known metal organic framework ZIF-8, silicon polymers based on PDMS with optimised optical and mechanical properties were developed as host materials. ZIF-8 nanocrystal integration into the polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) polymer changed the material's physical characteristics and improved the resulting film's permeability and CH₄ solubility. By varying ZIF-8/polymer weight ratio, the mechanical, viscous, and refractive indices of the ZIF-8 functionalised polymers were enhanced and then employed as the fibre coating. When exposed to different concentrations of CH₄ in N₂ carrier gas, optical fibres coated with MOF-functionalized polymers, both single-mode and multi-mode, displayed scaling changes in transmitted power. Changes in the refractive index of the polymer cladding upon CH₄ sorption caused shifts in the evanescent wave interactions with the sensor coating, which in turn caused variations in the transmitted power through the fibre. It was possible to use D-shaped single mode fibres along with multimode fibres to detect methane at a 1 % limit in nitrogen. Fig. 23 displays the schematic sketch for the sensor characterisation system [26].

5.2.8. A rapid and fully optical hydrogen sensor utilizing a gold-coated optical fiber functionalized with a metal–organic framework layer

One of the greatest subjects in hydrogen technology and safety is remote hydrogen detection, which can be done without the need for electronic components or high temperatures. Miliutina et al. designed and implement a novel hydrogen sensor based on optical fibre. The proposed sensor based on the gold-coated multimode fiber, offering the plasmon properties, decorated by IRMOF-20 layer to have high selectivity and affinity towards hydrogen. XPS, Raman, XRD, and BET techniques were used to study the production and characteristics of the IRMOF20 layer, which was developed utilising a surface aided approach. The apparent variations in the IRMOF-20 layer's refractive index caused by hydrogen sorption are indicated by simultaneous ellipsometry measurements. The plasmon band wavelength location and intensity both changed significantly as a result of the addition of hydrogen. Good selectivity towards hydrogen, very low temperature dependency, functionality at room temperature or lower, high response/recovery rate, and insensitivity to humidity as well as CO₂, CO, or NO₂ were the salient features of the proposed hydrogen sensors. Good reproducibility, long-term stability, and reversibility were also demonstrated by the suggested hydrogen sensor. Fig. 24 illustrates the proposed sensor structure's design and realisation. The fracturing of the fibre shell and the deposition of a thin noble metal coating on the fibre core provided the plasmon active fibre surface (Fig. 24 (a)). Spectral backdrop was created using the airborne spectrum. The next phase

Fig. 23. Representation of the sensor configuration [26]. Copyright (2020), Elsevier.

Fig. 24. Schematic diagram of construction and operation of the hydrogen sensor, based on IRMOF-20 coated film to provide a plasmon-active optical fibre surface [152]. Copyright (2019), American Chemical Society.

involved growing the IRMOF-20 layer with surface assistance in order to boost its affinity for hydrogen (Fig. 24 (b) and (c)). As a last step, hydrogen purging was used to assess the operation of the sensor (Fig. 24 (d)). In the enclosed space of the plasmon-active optical fibre portion, the thickness of the deposited MOF must be sufficiently large to cause a noticeable increase in refractive index [152].

5.2.9. An ultracompact gas sensor featuring metal-organic-framework-based differential fiber-optic Fabry-Perot nanocavities

One important optical sensing technique that can be used in a variety of spectral bands is refractive-index (RI)-based sensing. Although RI-based gas sensing has been widely employed for the detection of biological liquids, it is difficult to detect small-molecule gases in particular

because of the incredibly tiny RI shift due to changes in gas concentration. Kim et al. explained dual Fabry-Perot (FP) nanocavities based on MOF for an ultracompact fiber-optic differential gas sensor based on RI [162]. MOF can also be used as FP cavity material to boost the sensitivity as well as the selectivity to particular gas molecules. Comparing the differential sensing system to single FP cavity based sensing, the sensitivity is further increased because of the opposing change in the cavity-length-dependent reflection of the two FP cavities. Kim et al. developed, a fiber-optic CO₂ sensor with dual FP nanocavities based on ZIF-8 thin films of different thickness, as a prototype (Fig. 25 (a)). In order to acquire the highest positive (FP cavity 1) and negative (FP cavity 2) changes in the reflection with regard to the CO₂ exposure concurrently, the cavity lengths (i.e., the ZIF-8 film thicknesses: t_1 and t_2) are chosen for differential sensing [Fig. 25 (b)]. The sensor demonstrated an increased sensitivity of 48.5 mV/CO₂ vol%, a dynamic range of 0–100 CO₂ vol%, and a resolution of 0.019 CO₂ vol% with 1 Hz low-pass filtering. Its effective footprint was as small as 157 μm^2 [162].

5.3. MOF coated fiber optics biosensor

Zhu et al. studied MOF/Enzyme coated LPG fiber sensor for the detection of glucose [35]. Most crucial part of this study is the fabrication of the surface modified LPG sensor. To fabricate this sensor cleaned LPG fiber was modified by the PBS buffer to create negatively charged and further immersed in precursor solution containing Zn²⁺, 2-methylimidazole and GOx for 30 min. ZIF-8/GOx coated LPG fibers which is clearly shown in Fig. 26. SEM images of the naked and coated LPG fiber is shown in the Fig. 26 (c) and (d).

According to Fig. 27, in the sensor fabrication first inscribed grating on fiber where resonance wavelength of the grating fiber is 1538 nm. The resonance wavelength of the grating has been shifting to 1545 nm due to functionalization of high index of the biosensing layer on cladding [163]. The sensitivity of ZIF-8/GOx coated LPG to surrounding

Fig. 25. Schematic diagram of the ZIF-8-based dual FP nanocavity fiber-optic differential CO₂ sensor. (b) Fundamentals of differential CO₂ sensors [162]. Copyright (2020), Optica publishing group.

refractive index is around 280 nm/RIU, which confirms the negligible influence of biosensing layer on sensitivity. They have studied the glucose (concentration: mM to 10 mM) response with the bare and MOF coated enzyme fiber, only they observed shift in transmission spectra only for the coated LPG. They also measured the refractive index of the glucose concentration with abbe refractometer, there is only small shift (0.28 nm) in wavelength which confirmed the shift in wavelength with coated fiber only happens due to enzymatic reaction. The sensitivity of the MOF-Gox coated fiber is very high compared with Gox modified by covalent band, the large specific surface areas of ZIF-8 can absorb more GOx molecules in pores, which results in larger wavelength shift. To investigate the reusability of the sensor, the recycle measurements are applied and the results are shown in Figs. 28 and 29.

In this study, the same structure of ZIF-8/GOx was applied both in free form and on LPG (long-period gratings) to assess the performance of GOx. The catalytic ability of the ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG was evaluated by comparing it with the performance of free GOx encapsulated in ZIF-8. The sensor's selectivity and sensitivity are primarily determined by the catalytic reaction between GOx and glucose. For testing, various analytes were used in combination with ABTS + at 415 nm to measure absorbance spectra, highlighting the differences in sensor response. The ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG demonstrated excellent selectivity for glucose compared to other molecules, with a sensitivity more than ten times higher towards glucose than toward other compounds. When compared to free GOx, the GOx encapsulated in ZIF-8 exhibited significantly improved stability. This was demonstrated through a series of tolerance tests against organic solvents, with the results shown in Fig. 27. After immersion in ethanol for 30 min, free GOx almost completely lost its activity, while GOx integrated within ZIF-8 retained more than 97 % of its original enzymatic function. Additionally, the ZIF-8/GOx complex showed resistance to trypsin, a protease that typically degrades GOx, further confirming the protective effect of the ZIF-8 framework. These findings highlight the excellent stabilizing and protective properties of ZIF-8 for GOx encapsulation. Furthermore, the ZIF-8/GOx composite demonstrated impressive long-term storage stability. After being immersed in solution for one week, the composite maintained over 80 % of its activity, while free GOx exhibited a significant decline, losing nearly half of its enzymatic function. These results reinforce the high stability, selectivity, and long-term functionality of the ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG sensor when used for glucose detection. The reusability of the ZIF-8/GOx-modified LPG sensor was also evaluated, with glucose concentrations ranging from 0 to 4 mM. The results demonstrated the sensor's capacity to retain its sensing capabilities across multiple cycles, making it a reliable tool for repeated glucose detection. SEM imaging of the ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG sensor revealed that the biosensing layer remained largely unchanged after prolonged use, further corroborating the robustness and durability of the sensor. The stability and catalytic performance of the ZIF-8/GOx-modified LPG sensor underscore its potential for long-term applications in glucose detection and other biosensing tasks. A summary of the sensor's performance, including comparisons with other fiber-optic biosensors, is presented in Table 6, highlighting the superior characteristics of the ZIF-8/GOx composite in terms of stability, selectivity, and reusability.

5.3.1. A dependable sensor for dopamine detection, utilizing a gold nanoparticle/Cu-TCPP 2D MOF/gold/D-shaped fiber, leveraging both SPR and LSPR coupling mechanisms

The surface plasmon resonance (SPR)-based optical fiber sensor has gained significant popularity in biological detection due to its ability to offer real-time measurements with compact design features. One innovative approach, as explained by Gao et al., involves the development of a gold nanoparticle (AuNPs)/2-dimensional metal-organic framework (2D MOF Cu-TCPP)/gold/D-shaped fiber SPR sensor for the precise detection of dopamine. This unique sensor leverages a composite structure consisting of AuNPs combined with 2D MOFs and a gold-coated D-shaped fiber to enhance the sensor's performance. The

Fig. 26. (a) Schematic illustration and (b) SEM image of ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG, with inset showing SEM images of the bare LPG; microscope images of (c) bare LPG and (d) ZIF-8/GOx-coated LPG [35]. Copyright (2019), Elsevier.

Fig. 27. (a) Transmission spectra of LPG before ZIF-8/GOx modification and (b) after ZIF-8/GOx modification at varying glucose solution concentrations; (c) Refractive index data for different glucose concentrations (range: 0–1000 mM); (d) corresponding resonant wavelength shift as a function of glucose concentration [35]. Copyright (2019), Elsevier.

sensor's structure is carefully designed to optimize the coupling of SPR with local surface plasmon resonance (LSPR), which in turn significantly boosts the intensity of the surface electric field. This enhancement occurs due to the secondary amplification of signals, a result of increased intensity in the surface electric field and the deeper penetration of the

evanescent field. By maximizing the deposition concentration of AuNPs and 2D MOF, the sensor achieves a remarkable 104.61 % increase in sensitivity, as well as a 73.87 % rise in the figure of merit (FOM). This dual coupling of SPR and LSPR offers a substantial improvement in sensitivity, reaching an impressive 10,000 nm/RIU. In addition to these

Fig. 28. (a) Assessment of the selectivity of the ZIF-8/GOx composite, with solutions containing 1.0 mM of galactose, mannose, fructose, and lactose, 1 mg/ml of BSA, and 100 μ M of glucose, respectively; (b) Comparison of the stability of ZIF-8/GOx composite with free GOx; (c) Reusability of the ZIF-8/GOx-based LPG sensor across multiple glucose testing cycles (0–4 mM) [35]. Copyright (2019), Elsevier.

structural and design advancements, the sensor's sensitivity mechanism is explained through energy band theory, which emphasizes the key role played by the interaction between the material properties and the external analyte. The sensor demonstrated an exceptionally low limit of detection (LOD), achieving a value of $1.07 \pm 0.07 \times 10^{-14}$ M, which enables the detection of dopamine molecules in concentrations ranging from 5×10^{-7} M to 5×10^{-14} M [169]. By incorporating a DNA probe as a linker to specifically trap dopamine molecules, the sensor shows significant promise in achieving high specificity and reliability for biological applications. The study's results highlight that this sensor, with its low-cost fabrication, high sensitivity, and robust accuracy, provides an efficient solution for the detection of dopamine, making it an ideal tool for applications in medical diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and other areas requiring precise biomolecular detection. This combination of SPR and LSPR in an optical fiber sensor system offers exciting potential for advancing biosensing technology.

5.3.2. Highly sensitive Fiber-Optic SPR urea sensor based on ZIF-8/Urease

Based on the metal–organic zeolite framework (MOF), urease modification, and the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) phenomenon, Cheng et al. developed highly sensitive fiber-optic urea sensor [170]. In the multimode-thin core-multimode fibre (MMF) structure, which exhibited high refractive index sensitivity, the SPR effect was stimulated by plating gold layer on the thin core fibre (TCF). ZIF-8 was able to fully engage urea and immobilise additional urease during the rapid aqueous phase synthesis process, which resulted in the growth of the ZIF-8/urease composite film on the gold film. The measurement of urea concentration achieved with great sensitivity and good selectivity due to the urease-catalyzed urea hydrolysis would alter the refractive index. Its urea measurement sensitivity could exceed 6 nm/mM within the concentration range of 1–7 mM. The postulated sensor has a high potential for use in the field of monitoring human health. A marine light source with a wavelength range of 360–2000 nm, a sensor probe, and a marine spectrometer make up the SPR effect-based urea sensor system depicted in Fig. 30. A multimode fibre (MMF) is used to transmit the light that comes from the light source. When the sensor probe surface's refractive index changes, the excited SPR solid-phase resonance spectrum will also change. Two MMFs, a thin core fibre (TCF), and gold film plating on the TCF are the components of the developed structure, which is used to induce SPR. The M–T–M structure is the abbreviated term for the suggested structure. The two MMFs lower ends are aligned with the TCF, lining up the MMFs core with the TCF cladding. As a result, the majority of the light beams transmitted through the MMFs core will enter the TCF cladding, increasing the amount of evanescent waves and increasing the sensitivity of SPR to changes in the refractive index of the solution. Consequently, the M–T–M (dislocated) fibre structure SPR sensor has a

higher refractive index sensitivity. The refractive index decreases more with increasing urea solution concentration due to urease-catalyzed hydrolysis, and there is a more noticeable blue shift in the SPR wavelength. This permits highly sensitive urea concentration measurement.

6. MOF based photonic device: Photodetector

One of the key parts of optical integrated circuits for converting an optical signal into an electrical one is a photodetector. Numerous research studies have focused on the development and evaluation of traditional photodetectors that rely on inorganic materials, such as silicon, gallium nitride (GaN), gallium arsenide (GaAs), and other group III–V semiconductors [171]. These materials have long been favored due to their inherent properties, including high carrier mobility and robust device stability, which make them ideal for fabricating photodetectors with high sensitivity [172]. The covalent bonds between atoms in these materials contribute to their excellent electrical performance, enhancing their reliability in various applications. However, despite these advantages, their use is constrained by certain limitations, such as a narrow operational wavelength range resulting from their specific bandgaps and the complex and costly manufacturing processes involved. These challenges hinder the development of more versatile, flexible, and cost-effective photodetectors with broader spectral response ranges [173]. In recent years, attention has shifted toward utilizing organic semiconductors to address these limitations [124]. Organic semiconductors are typically composed of organic molecules or polymer chains that exhibit semiconducting properties. These materials have attracted significant interest due to their potential to offer more flexible and affordable alternatives to traditional inorganic semiconductors. Additionally, organic semiconductors can be engineered to have tunable bandgaps, allowing for the design of photodetectors with a wider response range and greater versatility. This flexibility, combined with their ease of processing, opens up new possibilities for the development of photodetectors that can be fabricated on lightweight, flexible substrates, making them ideal for a wide array of applications in emerging technologies, including wearable devices and large-area electronics.

Comparatively speaking, optical devices developed with inorganic semiconductors exhibit faster detection than those built using organic semiconductors. Organic-based device production is less costly, nevertheless. The benefit of both categories can therefore be obtained by combining two different types of semiconductors. One example of a device that could provide faster detection at reduced fabrication costs consists of one that combines organic and inorganic semiconductors and MOFs possess such characteristics [174]. MOFs have demonstrated intriguing characteristics including adjustable cavity size, high porosity, structural tunability and extraordinarily large surface area [175]. Even

Fig. 29. (a) An illustration showing a microfluidic device which detected dopamine solutions; (b) dopamine solutions at varying concentrations exhibited variations in resonance wavelength; (c) the sensor resonance wavelength and dopamine concentrations have a linear relationship.. (d) comparing, under the identical experimental settings, the sensor response to targeted dopamine (5×10^{-9} M), ascorbic acid (5×10^{-3} M), and uric acid (5×10^{-3} M). (e) change in dopamine resonance wavelength in serum solution at varying doses. (f) linear connection between the sensor's resonant frequency and serum dopamine concentration [169]. Copyright (2024), Elsevier.

Table 6
Performances studies of different type of fiber optic biosensor.

S. No.	Advantages/Disadvantages	Target analyte	Sensor configurations	Concentration range	Sensitivity	Detection limit	References
1	Highly selective and sensitive	Glucose	ZIF-8/Gox coated on fiber	1 mM-10 mM	0.5 nm/mM	0.01 mM	[35]
2	High sensitivity, wide operating range, reusable, considerable selectivity	Phenolic compounds	Enzyme (tyrosinase) entrapped gel coated on gold coated fiber	0 μ M – 1000 μ M	0.032 nm/ μ M	11 μ M	[164]
3	Worked close to physiological range	Urea	Enzyme (Urease) entrapped gel coated on silver coated fiber	0–160 mM	0.20 nm/mM	–	[165]
4	Highly integrated, flexible, and miniaturized in situ biosensor	ssDNA	Graphene-gold coated on fiber	1×10^{-12} to 10×10^{-6} M	–	–	[166]
5	Poor Sensitivity	heamoglobin	graphene-MoS2 coated D-shaped PCF SPR sensor	0 g/L to 241 g/L	0.7 nm/(g/L)	–	[167]
6	Not defined	DNA molecules	Hollow core fiber filled with DNA molecules	5 μ M	–	–	[168]

Fig. 30. (a) Illustration of the detection equipment; (b) arrangement for structure detection; (c) an angle view of the sensing region.

the smallest changes in the arrangement of metals and ligands within Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) can significantly enhance their mechanical and optical properties. This remarkable structural tunability allows for precise control over the materials' characteristics, facilitating improved optical absorption capabilities. As a result, the enhanced structural flexibility and optimization of the metal–ligand interactions lead to better quantum efficiency, which in turn amplifies the materials' ability to absorb light and convert it into electrical signals. This enhanced optical absorption directly contributes to improving the photodetectors' responsiveness to light, increasing their sensitivity and efficiency in capturing and converting light into electrical energy. Through these adjustments, MOFs exhibit superior electric responses, making them highly suitable for a wide range of applications in optical devices, including sensors, detectors, and energy-harvesting technologies. Because of its distinct structural characteristics, tunability, benefits from both organic and inorganic components, and adaptability, MOF is anticipated to surpass more conventional semiconductor materials in the microelectronics sector. Additionally, Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) films are increasingly favored over traditional materials in the fields of optoelectronics and nanotechnology due to their ability to reduce the material consumption required for device construction [176]. Unlike conventional materials, which often necessitate larger quantities of raw materials for fabrication, MOF films offer the advantage of being highly efficient in their use of material while still providing excellent performance. This characteristic is particularly valuable when designing compact and lightweight devices, as it allows for the creation of thinner, more efficient layers without compromising on the functionality or performance of the device. Furthermore, the versatility of MOFs enables the tailoring of their properties, making them highly adaptable for various applications, ranging from sensors to energy storage and conversion devices, all while minimizing the overall material footprint. Considering the fledgling state of this area of research, it is essential to provide an overview of the chronicled MOF-based photodetectors and discuss their auspicious prospects for use. Here, we discussed the advancements made in MOF-based photodetectors in recent years.

6.1. Classification of photodetectors based on MOFs

The classification of MOF-based photodetectors as follows:

6.1.1. MOF single crystal

Due to their flawless structure without grain boundaries and advantageous properties that affect the material inherent conductivity, single crystal constitute excellent candidates for optoelectronic devices [177]. There are numerous ways for developing MOF single crystals, such as solvothermal technique, slow diffusion, hydrothermal, electrochemical, mechanochemical, microwave assisted heating, ultrasound, and more [178,179]. The majority of MOF single crystals used to create photodetectors currently manufactured via the hydro(solvo)thermal technique.

6.1.1.1. Hydro thermal / solvo thermal technique. A particular molar ratio of metals and ligands added to the autoclave, in this liquid phase synthesis procedure, mixture is then allowed to react for a pre-determined period of time at a predetermined temperature (Fig. 31(a)) [180,181]. When reactants have high boiling points, autoclaves lined with polytetrafluoroethylene are typically utilized. A specific solvent will be used, depending on the type of MOF crystal. DMF, DMSO, H₂O, and EtOH are the most often utilised solvents; combinations of these solvents also occasionally used. This approach yields MOF crystals with good quality that are appropriate for structural characterisation [182]. In presence of benzoic acid, Wang et al. used a hydrothermal process to produce nano-sized UiO-66-NH₂ (Fig. 31(b)) [183]. Subsequently they exploited UiO-66-NH₂ as a self-calibration nanoprobe to selectively detect and visualize hypochlorite biologically. UiO-66-NH₂ exhibited luminescence at 432 nm under 400 nm excitation, and a new luminescence at 533 nm upon the addition of ClO⁻ group. As ClO⁻ content rises, also increases the emission intensity at 533 nm. The detection signal of ClO⁻ can be efficiently identified by UiO-66-NH₂ through the use of the ratio of I₅₃₃/I₄₃₃ nm. With solvothermal process, Guo et al. were able to successfully produce novel MOF (Fig. 31(c)) [184]. The first rewritable radiochromic semiconductor material is this MOF. It exhibits photo-current and a distinct colour shift when exposed to X-rays (like K_α rays from Mo, Cu, or Al anode). Additionally, Wang et al. used solvothermal technique to synthesise RhB⁺ @TbATAB (Fig. 31(d)) [185].

6.1.2. MOF thin film

When it comes to a wider range of uniform coverage and better practical usefulness, MOF in thin-film form has an advantage over powder or crystal MOF materials due to its continuous density and large specific surface area [187,188]. When incorporating conductive MOF

Fig. 31. (a) Illustration of solvothermal technique; crystal structure of (b) UiO-66-NH₂; (c) (EV)[Zn₂(ox)₃]•3.5H₂O; RhB⁺@TbTATAB [186]. Copyright (2024), Springer Nature.

into optoelectronic devices, high-quality thin-film samples are an excellent option [189,190]. According to Lu et al., thin film production, contact development, and circuit design are the fundamental issues with semiconductor MOF integration in active devices [191]. Recently, a number of methods for generating MOF films on substrates have been devised.

6.1.2.1. Interfacial synthesis technique. This method regulates the development of MOF thin film via the liquid/liquid or liquid/air interface. The nucleation and development of MOF may be precisely regulated since the reaction occurs at the solvent interface. In particular, by taking advantage of the excellent dispersion of organic ligands on the liquid surface, liquid/air interface synthesis may regulate the thickness of MOF thin films. MOF thin film preparation has been done extensively using this technique [192]. In order to efficiently synthesise 2D Ni MOF nanosheets with controlled molar ratios of metal precursors and organic linkers (RM/L), Huang et al. developed a mild liquid–liquid interfacial reaction technique. These NSs can be used directly as reliable and efficient electrocatalysts for the two-electron oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in alkaline solution. The interface reaction technique to generate Ni MOF nanosheets shown in Fig. 34 [193].

6.1.2.2. Deposition of powdered MOF-based technique. Through this method, MOF thin films are obtained from MOF powder. Direct drop-casting powder MOF onto suitable substrates or prepatterned metal electrodes allows for easy deposition [194]. To develop a porous MOF thin film, Kazemzad et al. choose zeolite imidazolium framework (ZIF) and filled it with porous silicon (PS) [195]. Semiconductor photodetectors are made using ZIF/PS MOF thin films. It becomes apparent that at low temperatures, the photocurrent is significantly photosensitive to UV radiation and is temperature-dependent.

6.1.2.3. Layer-by-layer technique. The advantages of the MOF thin film developed with this technology comprise good homogeneity, controlled film thickness, and precise growth orientation. The substrate must first be functionalised to provide coordination sites for MOF growth before MOF thin films can be generated. In order to prepare the MOF thin film, the functional substrate was first submerged in the coordination of metal salt solution and metal nodes, after which the substrate was cleaned with solvent. subsequently the organic ligand solution was submerged in the ligand for additional coordination assembly, and the sample was once

more cleaned with solvent [196–198]. Cu₃(HHTT)₂ thin film was used by Yan et al. to develop a flexible photodetector that demonstrated a consistent light response at room temperature over the ultraviolet to mid-infrared wavelength range [199]. Compared to the broadband photodetectors, it is substantially wider. Recently, they used layer-by-layer (LBL) method of liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) to generate In-TCPP films on SiO₂/Si substrates (Fig. 32), and constructed photodetectors. With a quick rise/fall time (0.07/0.04 s) and large detectivity (D*) of 7.28 × 10¹⁴ Jones, the photoelectric detector performs better in light detection [172].

6.1.2.4. Chemical vapour deposition (CVD) technique. Chemical vapour deposition (CVD) technology develops thin films by depositing vaporised solid materials on a variety of substrates using a top-down method. During the CVD deposition of ligands, the pre-deposited metal oxide layer is converted into the appropriate MOF structure, allowing for the vapor-phase development of MOF thin films. Even on surfaces with different forms, the CVD approach could generate high-quality, directionally formed thin films that are impervious to solvent damage and offer a uniform thickness of low-porosity coatings [200]. This provides novel opportunities to transform semiconductor MOF into useful gadgets. With the CVD technique, for instance, Park et al. synthesised large-area, highly orientated two-dimensional conductive MOF sheets (Cu₃(C₆O₆)₂) [201]. After that, they used electron beam lithography to produce thin-film microdevices that could conduct up to 92.95 S cm⁻¹.

6.1.3. MOF composites

A multipurpose MOF has an innate multiple charge-transfer mechanism between the metal and the ligand, which allows it to have optimised optical properties. Its enormous porosity, low conductivity, and inadequate crystallinity, however, prevented it from being commercialised [202]. Better-performing composites can be developed by combining MOF with additional materials. The typical process to generate MOF composites involves growing MOF thin films on composite materials like graphene and ZnO [202–204]. Recently, ZIF-8@ZnO core–shell nanorod array/Si heterojunction self-powered photodetector was developed by Xue et al. to address the slow sensing and unexpected response to visible light produced by the surface imperfections of ZnO [204]. The Schottky junction on the top electrode of ZIF-8/Si is then combined to develop a photodetector. Its response rate, achieved by hydrogenation and ZIF-8 combination treatment, is over five times higher than that of the original ZnO nanorods array/Si

Fig. 32. Illustration of MOF implementation via layer by layer dipping process on a modified surface [172]. Copyright (2021), John Wiley and Sons.

heterojunction photodetector. And photodetector's photo-response properties are much improved. With a high response rate of around $7.07 \times 10^4 \text{ mA W}^{-1}$, the photodetector exhibited a high detection rate of approximately 2.14×10^{16} Jones. Self-powered photodetectors, especially for 2 and 0-dimensional materials, can be distinguished from it. With the use of post-processing techniques, it is possible to develop high-performance self-powered photodetectors with significant potential applications.

6.2. MOF based photodetectors

MOFs have great potential as optoelectronic materials since they combine exceptional photophysical properties with the ability to precisely tune the organic and inorganic components of them in order to achieve the desired performance. The tunability of MOFs allows them to be used in a variety of advanced photonic applications due to their versatility. Tian et al. demonstrated, for instance, that metal-oxo strands can be used as a primary structure in a MOF-based system to create 1D chromophore arrays exhibiting enhanced optical properties, by using the metal-oxo strands as the primary structure [172]. Additionally, porphyrinic groups, known for their distinctive photophysical properties, enable highly sensitive photodetectors. The layers of In-TCPP thin films were assembled layer-by-layer in a [021] orientation using a layer-by-layer assembly technique. A columnar arrangement of porphyrins was formed using $\text{In}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and TCPP (5,10,15,20-(4-carboxyphenyl) porphyrin). A highly anisotropic frontier orbital is generated by this alignment of porphyrins, which contributes to their remarkable photo-activity. An impressive 7.28×10^{14} Jones photoresponsivity was observed in the MOF thin films, together with rising and falling times of 0.07 and 0.04 s. This MOF-based photodetector demonstrates remarkable sensitivity when compared to other organic materials. It opens the door to innovative optoelectronic devices with enhanced performance and potential for commercialization based on regular arrays of organic semiconductors built from stable, inorganic lead structures. Owing to their superior physical and chemical properties, MOF materials have lately led to the development of various significant optoelectronic device applications, including X-ray, UV/vis, and NIR photodetectors as well as electrochemical bioanalysis detection. Recently, tremendous

advancements in MOF-based photodetectors, as well as growing number of researchers are focussing on this noteworthy category.

6.2.1. X-ray photodetector

Numerous industries, including national security, defence, healthcare, nondestructive testing, and the nuclear sector, depend heavily on X-ray testing [42]. Because of a phenomena known as vignetting in non-planar landscapes, several X-ray exposures are required to assure imaging quality, which puts the human body at risk for radiation exposure [205]. It is therefore anticipated that a flexible detector with the shortest exposure time and frequency will be developed. There are two basic categories of X-ray detectors: indirect-type and direct-type [206]. When deploying an indirect conversion X-ray detector, light is initially produced by a scintillating phosphor, then photodiode arrays are used to detect the light that emerges from the scintillator [207]. It has been established recently with MOF's and make them potentially useful for X-ray detection [206]. Lin et al. firstly explained MOF based X-ray excitation luminescence [208]. The synthesis of MOF was carried out using anthracene-based emitters as bridging ligands and high-Z metal clusters as connection nodes (Fig. 33 (a)). Hf-MOF produced a greater signal than Zr-MOF because Hf had bigger X-ray scattering cross section than Zr (Fig. 33 (b)). Furthermore, in comparison to the component, MOF exhibited outstanding X-ray to light convergence ability because of the synergistic action of bridging ligands as light emitters and heavy metal clusters as X-ray antennae (Fig. 33 (c)). Monguzzi et al. reported a composite scintillator based on MOF nanocrystals embedded in polymer matrix (Fig. 33 (d)) with the same organic linker and a Zr-based metal cluster ($\text{Zr}_6\text{O}_4(\text{OH})_4(\text{CO}_2)_{12}$) [209]. Ionising radiation and complex components interact to sensitise the singlet molecular exciton formed on the ligand, which leads to radiation recombination that produces fluorescence with strong radioluminescence stability (Fig. 33 (e)). Light scattering primarily has little effect on the nano composites, which exhibit an ultrafast scintillation rise time of about 50 ps (Fig. 33 (f)). Another anthracene nuclear derivative (2E, 2E)-3,3'-(anthracene-9,10-diyl) diacrylic acid (H_2adda) was used by Guo et al. to synthesise X-ray responsive Scintillating MOF (SMOF) with good radioluminescence stability (Fig. 33 (g)) [210]. Additionally, MOF-based flexible scintillator film (Fig. 33 (h)) has been used for X-ray imaging for the first time,

Fig. 33. (a) Comparable structural models observed from the angle. Blue polyhedra: eight coordinating oxygen atoms in Hf^{4+} or Zr^{4+} ; red, grey, and white balls represent oxygen, carbon, and hydrogen, respectively; (b) mechanism of oscillation of Zr- and Hf-MOF; (c) Zr-based MOF crystal structure; (d) summary of the photophysics in the scintillation technique; (e) growth in response to pulsating X-ray stimulus; (f) crystal structure of $[Pb(ada)(DMF)]$; (g) development in response to pulsating X-ray stimulus; (h) images of Pb-MOF flexible film [186]. Copyright (2024), Springer Nature. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 34. (a) Schematic diagram of detector based on SCU-12. The representation of the detection equipment in inset; (b) an illustration of SCU-12 crystal structure. Where, Tb (green), Cl (blue), and yellow (benzene ring) are the colour codes; (c) photocurrent generated by X-rays versus dose rate [211] Copyright (2019), American Chemical Society; (d) the experimental device illustration for (EV) $[Zn_2(ox)_3] \cdot 3.5H_2O$; (e) crystal structure of (EV) $[Zn_2(ox)_3] \cdot 3.5H_2O$; (f) A bias voltage of 30 V for 2A was used to measure the photocurrent density vs dosage rate [186]. Copyright (2024), Springer Nature. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

obtaining a high spatial resolution of 5.5 lp mm^{-1} . It showed potential utility of a flexible MOF-based scintillator in X-ray imaging and offers an efficient visualisation tool for X-ray imaging.

In contrast to materials utilised in indirect detection that rely on scintillators, semiconductors have the ability to directly transform X-ray photons into carriers that enhanced energy and spatial resolution [207]. Wang et al. examined semiconductor MOF direct radiation sensing [211]. Under continuous hard X-ray radiation (Fig. 34 (a)), they demonstrate the successful conversion of X-ray photons to electrical current signals by a lanthanide-based semiconductive MOF (Fig. 34 (b)). Under 80 kV_p X-ray irradiation, the polycrystalline detection device based on semiconductor MOF has an X-ray sensitivity of $23.8 \mu\text{C Gy}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 34 (c)), which comparable with selenium detectors that amorphous on market. The detector features include a low dose rate detection limit and good radiation stability while operating. For the first time, Guo et al. explained, X-ray detectors developed via rewritable radiochromic semiconductor MOF materials (Fig. 34 (d), (e)) [184]. As shown in Fig. 34 (f), the sensitivity of the semiconductor single crystal detector is $3216 \mu\text{C Gy}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, surpassing the sensitivity of all commercial α -Se detectors and all other MOF-based detectors.

A flexible X-ray detector was proposed by Ren et al [100], with the absorption layer containing Ni-DABDT (DABDT = 2,5-diamino-1,4-benzenedithiol dihydrochloride) MOF (Fig. 34 (a)). The detector operates at an exceptionally high sensitivity of $98.6 \mu\text{C Gy}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 34 (b)), with a low detection limit of $7.2 \mu\text{Gy}_{\text{air}} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for radiation robustness, by directly converting X-ray photons into carriers. A novel possibility to realise a low-Z (atomic number) MOF large-area high-sensitivity X-ray imager is rendered possible by the detector. The photoelectric characteristics of semiconductor materials are significantly influenced by exciton behaviour, which has not yet been well studied in the MOF [185,212]. According to Wang et al., framework-guest interaction can control the exciton behaviour in semiconductor MOF [185]. Effective energy transfer from the MOF skeleton to the molecular receptor is caused by the binding of electron defect molecules in the pores of the terbium-based semiconductor MOF. The energy is transferred from the molecular receptor to the MOF skeleton. The unique exciton type conversion is encouraged by this interaction, which improves conductivity and photoelectric qualities. After exciton conversion, the photocurrent

on/off ratio increased from 1.2 to 79.5. The apparatus achieves an exceptionally low detection limit of $4.42 \mu\text{Gy}_{\text{air}} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a sensitivity of $51.9 \mu\text{C Gy}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Growing high-quality single crystals adequate in size to construct devices is a significant challenge in the design of semiconductor MOFs [42]. Wang et al. utilised the large crystal material of SCU-15 to fabricate a single crystal X-ray detector (Fig. 35) and further constructed a planar 2×3 pixel detector to demonstrate its potential application in X-ray imaging [42]. They carried out this issue by adjusting the crystal morphology by controlling the reaction to obtain SCU-15 crystals of different sizes. The SCU-15 single crystal device surpasses the particle powder device in the field of detection performance while the crystal possesses a high quality. As shown in Fig. 34 (f), the detector detection sensitivity is $33.96 \mu\text{Gy}_{\text{air}} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and it is stable. The MOF-based X-ray photodetector device performance is compiled in Table 6.

Table 7 showed MOFs based X-ray photodetector efficiency.

6.2.2. UV/Vis photodetector

In the domains of research, industry, the environment, and medicine, ultraviolet (UV) radiation detection is crucial [216]. For instance, human health will be impacted by prolonged exposure to UV radiation [217]. MOF are appealing for a variety of ultraviolet applications because of their high compatibility, adjustable characteristics, and

Table 7
X-ray photodetector efficiency based on MOFs.

Material	Methodology of preparation	Application	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{C Gy}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	References
Zr/Hf-MOF	Solvothermal	Scintillator	–	[208]
Zn-MOF	Solvothermal	Semiconductors	3216	[181]
SCU-15	Solvothermal	Semiconductors	3.51	[42]
Ni-DABDT MOFs	Solvothermal	Semiconductors	98.6	[213]
SMOFs	Solvothermal	Scintillator	–	[214]
TbTATAB	Solvothermal	Semiconductors	51.9	[182]
Pb-sMOF	Solvothermal	Scintillator	–	[215]
SCU-12	Solvothermal	Semiconductors	23.8	[211]

Fig. 35. (a) Representation of the Ni-DABDT MOF-based X-ray prototype imaging device; (b) Ni-DABDT MOF crystal structure; (c) plot demonstrates the photocurrent generated by X-rays and its dosage rate dependency [213] Copyright (2021), American Chemical Society; (d) The illustration of device under X-ray radiation; (e) SCU-15 crystal structures; (f) relationship between the X-ray dose rate and the signal-to-noise ratio [42]. Copyright (2022) Elsevier Ltd.

appropriate ultraviolet absorption. In the field of photodetection, Lanthanide Metal-Organic Frameworks (Ln-MOF) exhibit intriguing physical and chemical properties together with a notable degree of structural variety. Bark et al. described the application of Eu-MOF as core material in selective UVC detector (Fig. 36 (a)) [218], since Wang et al. developed the first lanthanum-based photodetector to monitor ultraviolet radiation [219]. In UVC PD, Eu-MOF serves as a broad-band gap light absorber (Fig. 36 (b)). The device possesses beneficial features such as self-powered operation, high switching ratio of 107.33, fast response time of 98/122 ms (rise/fall time), robust inhibitory ability to UVA and visible light, and good response to UV radiation at a wavelength of 254 nm. Moreover, a month after remaining in the air, the unpacked UVC PD retains nearly continuous light response. When operating at zero bias voltage, the Eu-MOF photodetector can efficiently detect the UV radiation from methanol fires (Fig. 36 (c)). Zeng et al. recently described an analysis of layer-by-layer (LBL) deposition-fabricated $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HHTP})_2/\text{ZnO}$ type-II heterojunction UV photodetector [203]. Fig. 36 (d) illustrated the flow of carriers within the device, whereas Fig. 36 (e) represents the vertical structure of the photodetector during fabrication. The device reached a 3.8×10^9 Jones detectivity at 1 V and a responsivity of 78.2 A W^{-1} . Specifically, this self-powered device has an incredibly quick response time of 70 μs , the fastest of all MOF-based photodetectors and competitive with both organic and inorganic photodetectors. Moreover, the flexible gadget maintains its performance even after 1000 cycles of 180° bending.

The Schottky junction, which forms at the junction of metal and semiconductor, is highly advantageous in photodetectors because it has an inherent electric field [220–222]. Nevertheless, Schottky junctions are not as useful in self-powered devices due to the low efficiency of photogenerated electron/hole separation and transmission. The challenge has been addressed by Xu et al. by including electronically conductive MOF (EC-MOF) materials into the connection [223]. It is possible to adjust the Schottky junction of ϕ_B by using superior EC MOF thin films with flexible, tunable crystal and electronic structure. High-quality $\text{Cu}_3(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_6(\text{NH})_6)_2$ thin film was inserted to realise the first metal/n-Si Schottky diode that operated on its own. Fig. 36 (f) depicted the Schottky diode device structure and photoelectric performance, whereas Fig. 36 (g) displayed the typical rectification characteristics

that demonstrated the presence of a Schottky junction in the device. With a quick rise (0.007 s) and fall time (0.03 s), the self-powered photodetector based on EC-MOF exhibited a broad detectable spectral range (250–1500 nm) and a high external quantum efficiency (84 %).

Due to its exceptional optoelectronic capabilities and unique mechanical characteristics, graphene, a single layer 2D honeycomb lattice, has attracted a lot of interest lately for application in the development of flexible and stretchable devices [224]. Nevertheless, single-layer graphene is unable to generate ultrahigh light sensitivity because of its low light absorption ($\sim 2.3\%$) [225]. Recently, Chen et al. described the first wearable, broadband, and extremely sensitive photodetector on a polydimethylsiloxane substrate by combining the outstanding MOF characteristic with ultrahigh graphene carrier mobility [224]. In addition, Chen et al. used a graphene/MOF/graphene/poly heterojunction on a flexible polydimethylsiloxane substrate to combine the excellent features of a versatile MOF with monolayer graphene to report a self-powered, ultrafast (response time $\approx 220 \mu\text{s}$) and ultrasensitive (external quantum efficiency $\approx 3 \times 10^{10}\%$) wearable vertical phototransistor [202]. Additionally, numerous researchers explore photoelectrochemical photodetectors [226,227]. Recently, Wang et al. used hydrothermal technique to successfully synthesise a new MOF host-guest material $[\text{Cd}_3(\text{EtOIPA})_4(\text{HAD})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [227]. The protonated acridine (AD) cations serve as the template encapsulated inside the grids of the MOF trinucleate Cd (II) based 2D double-layer. It is an excellent self-driving photodetector due to based on photochemical assessments, the high photocurrent density ratio under both light and dark circumstances is 290 at 0 V bias potential. Recently, Feng et al. discussed, the photodetector of In_2O_3 -based PEC UV PDs [226]. Large specific surface area semiconductors are advantageous for producing high-performance photodetectors due to the charge transfer of semiconductors in PEC PDs (Fig. 37 (a)). Large specific surface area semiconductors are useful for producing high-performance photodetectors due to the charge transfer of semiconductors in PEC PDs (Fig. 37 (b)). With a high response rate of 21.19 mA W^{-1} and a high specific detection rate of 2.03×10^{10} Jones, this device also exhibited good UV light responsiveness (Fig. 37 (c)). Furthermore, under 365 nm irradiation, In_2O_3 MR PEC PD exhibited strong multi-circulation and long-term stability. The device performance of MOF-based UV-Vis photodetectors summarised in

Fig. 36. (a) An illustration of UV photodetector; (b) transport charge carriers under UVC light and in the dark; (c) detected signal current during the ignition of methanol indoors [218] Copyright (2022), American Chemistry Society; (d) $\text{Cu}_3(\text{HHTP})_2/\text{ZnO}$ heterojunction energy band; (e) schematic representation of the device structure demonstrated the light source coming from bottom [203] Copyright (2018) WILEY-VCH; (f) Ag/EC-MOF/n-Si Schottky diode device fabrication and photoelectric performance; (g) graph demonstrating the voltage and current of the device [223] Copyright (2020), Royal Society of Chemistry.

Fig. 37. (a) An illustration of PEC UV photodiodes; (b) PEC UV PD in comparison to several solid-state UV PD; (c) long-term stability and multicycle behaviour of In_2O_3 MR PEC PDs exposed to 100 cycles of 365 nm radiation [226] Copyright (2022), American Chemical Society.

Table 8

UV/Vis –ray photodetector efficiency based on MOFs.

MOF Material	Methodology of preparation	Wavelength (nm)	Detectivity (Jones)	References
$\text{Cu}_3(\text{HHTP})_2$	Layer-by-layer of MOF on ZnO	365	3.8×10^9	[218]
Eu-MOF	Spin-coating	254	1.015×10^{10}	[219]
Sr-MOF	Spin coated on top of graphene	325	6.9×10^{14}	[202]
Cd-MOF	Solvothermal	359	–	[226]
MIL-68	Direct mixing of MOF with PVDF	365	2.03×10^{10}	[227]
In-MOF	Layer-by-layer	420	7.28×10^{14}	[228]
Zn-MOF	Layer-by-layer	420	8.1×10^{13}	[229]

Table 7.

Table 8 showed the efficiency of MOF based UV/Vis-ray photodetector.

6.2.3. NIR photodetector

The sun emits variety of invisible radiation, including infrared light, which can be divided into three categories: near infrared (NIR), medium infrared (MIR), and far infrared (FIR). Among them, due to its exceptional and unique performance, NIR with 0.7–2.5 μm wavelength range is essential in a variety of applications such as optical communication, medical diagnosis, and military defence [230,231]. The MOF-based NIR photodetector is still difficult to implement, though. Because of their distinct structure and photoelectric qualities, two-dimensional layered materials (2DLMs) were considered to be the most promising options for the upcoming generation of high-performance infrared optoelectronic device [232]. However, the performance of 2DLM-based photodetectors fails to meet the demands of real-world applications because of their low optical absorption [233]. In order to develop high-performance near-infrared detectors (Fig. 38 (a)), Zhai et al. recently proposed combining MOF (Ni-CAT-1, Fig. 38 (b)) nanoparticles with good optical absorption

Fig. 38. (a) Schematic representation of hybrid heterojunction of 2D Bi_2Se_3 /MOF; (b) crystal structure of MOF (Ni-CAT-1); (c) band diagram of heterojunction photodetector under light; (d) chemical structure of MOF film, where, benzene rings represented by grey, sulphur atoms by yellow, and iron atoms by red spheres; (e) illustration of a $\text{Fe}_3(\text{THT})_2(\text{NH}_4)_3$, 2D MOF film monolayer; (f) I-V curves for various power densities at 77 K for a wavelength of 785 nm [186]. Copyright (2024), Springer Nature. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

characteristics and 2DLM that has excellent mobility [234]. At 1500 nm, the photodetector demonstrated an excellent detectivity of 3.5×10^{13} Jones and a high responsiveness of 4725 A W^{-1} . Because of the improved optical absorption and photogating effect working in concert, the hybrid heterojunction performs exceptionally well (Fig. 38 (c)). With semiconducting $\text{Fe}_3(\text{THT})_2(\text{NH}_4)_3$ two-dimension (2D) MOF thin films, Erbe et al. described a photodetector device (Fig. 38 (d), (e)) that functions throughout a wide spectrum range [235]. Visible to near-infrared (400–1575 nm) is a broad wavelength range which detected by device. This temperature-dependent photoconductivity of the active MOF layer demonstrated by Fig. 38 (f), which displayed an increase in photocurrent as photon density increases. The performance of the device is much better at 77 K. A voltage response rate, noise equivalent power, and specific detection rate, were higher at $7 \times 10^8 \text{ cm Hz}^{1/2} \text{ W}^{-1}$, when excited at 785 nm. These materials constitute intriguing possibilities for various optoelectronic applications due to their large-area coverage, cost-effective manufacturing of 2D conjugated MOF, and synthetic flexibility [235].

Due to their weak electrical conductivity and low chemical stability, quantum dots prevented the development of many photoelectric applications [236]. A hybrid composite material (PbS@MOF) consisting of conductive MOF (Ni-HHTP) and PbS quantum dots was developed by Lin and Fang et al. for applications in short-wave infrared detection [237]. PbS@MOF film efficiency was assessed by incorporating it into graphene field-effect transistor (FET) devices, which resulted in a high response rate of 301 A W^{-1} at around 1400 nm. Additionally, the chemical stability of the quantum dots is much improved by the presence of MOF. When compared to their crystalline counterparts, amorphous MOFs (aMOFs) have benefits including no crystal boundaries, isotropy, flexibility, and a large number of defect-induced active sites [238]. HKUST-1 single crystals were used by Milichko et al. to develop a single crystal photodetector with a spectral range of 600–1000 nm [239]. When heated by photoinduced heating, HKUST-1 crystals lose some of their optical and electrical characteristics. This photodetector response rate is 0.1 s which made possible by coordinated water molecules quick and reversible desorption process.

6.2.4. Light detection via Circular polarisation

Light by nature is polarised, and the detection of circularly polarised light (CPL) is important for quantum optics, quantum computing, and optical communication, among other areas [240,241]. Micro-integrated CPL detectors are difficult to build because traditional techniques of

detecting circularly polarised light require several optical components. In order to produce distinct excitations while absorbing left-handed CPL (LCP) and right-handed CPL (RCP) photons, the material needs to possess handedness photoelectric qualities [242]. Photodetectors based on chiral materials can directly detect CPL because chiral materials absorb LCP and RCP differently. As effective spin polarisation flexible photodetectors, Chen et al. developed chiral metal–organic frameworks (CMOF) based on non-chiral building blocks [243]. With a spin polarisation flexible detector, the CPL identified an anisotropy factor (g_{ph}) of 0.38 and the detection rate (D^*) was 1.83×10^{12} Jones. CMOF exhibits great optical gain and optical responsiveness. Chiral ligands can be directly chosen to give MOF chirality for the purpose of detecting circularly polarised light, based on the structural tunability of MOF. The homo chiral BINOL group was utilised by Lars et al. to functionalise porphyrin molecules. When dissolved, the porphyrin portion is planar [244]. However, the porphyrin portion gained chirality when it joined forces with zinc acetate to create SUR- MOF. Circularly polarised light exhibits chirality-dependent photoconduction, with an asymmetry coefficient g of 4.3×10^{-4} . Many organic materials will be able to exhibit outstanding chiral and optoelectronic properties owing to this assembly-induced chirality. Using a layer-by-layer approach, Gu et al. produced a pair of chiral SURMOF with orientation [245]. An anisotropy factor of up to 0.41 was obtained by further integrating SURMOF with extremely sensitive photodetectors. Furthermore, there were notable variations in the absorption of amino acid enantiomers in SURMOF (Fig. 39). It is demonstrated that MOF film has tremendous promise in chiral analysis by manufacturing D- and L-tryptophan sensor devices employing CP light. This finding provides new opportunities for the use of devices based on chiral MOF materials in the future.

7. Challenges and future prospect

In recent years, due to faster data transmission and consumption through visible light communication (VLC) compared to IR frequency systems, metal organic frameworks (MOFs) and MOFs-derived composite materials are the most promising materials. However, despite their improved PL properties, a number of issues prevent these materials from achieving a suitable frequency bandwidth and, consequently, from obtaining an extended response in the UV–vis–NIR spectrum: (i) The fabrication of MOFs necessitates several reaction steps, and the yield from these products is typically quite low, impeding their industrial potential. Additionally, the majority of products do not exhibit a high

Fig. 39. Schematic illustration of the device utilised for signal analysis to identify enantiomers [245]. Copyright (2023), American Chemical Society.

photoluminescence yield (PLQY), indicating that non-radiative recombination is aided (loss of anticipated emission features) and that the photoluminescence lifetime of certain light converters is in the microsecond range. This drawback postpones radiative recombination and makes it challenging to produce a frequency response at longer wavelengths; (ii) Despite the commercialization of some “star” MOFs like ZIF-8, MIL-100, HKUST-1, etc., it is still very difficult to design and construct low-cost MOFs with high yields; new organic linkers must be created through organic synthesis, and some metal precursors are highly expensive. In general, the process of developing MOFs is labor-intensive and time-consuming; (iii) As a result, a thorough grasp of the growth mechanism is extremely important to develop MOFs with a specific framework, amendable composition, and uniform or hierarchical porosity; the intrinsic self-assembly mechanism of MOFs is nevertheless unclear; (iv) MOFs fail to provide enough chemical, mechanical, or thermal stability; (v) The microporous nature of MOFs or MOFs-based materials may present mass transfer restrictions for bigger products and substrates; hierarchically porous MOF architecture may offer a novel way to overcome this problem; (vi) For quick charge transfer in electrocatalytic and photocatalytic applications, enhanced conductivity of MOFs is widely desired; (vii) It is imperative to address the practical difficulties of hazardous gas adsorption/desorption kinetics, cost, availability, reusability, and long-term stability of MOFs towards corrosive gases; (viii) If MOF adsorbents get improved, it is anticipated that they will be very important in the field of CO₂ capture because of their high stability, which will increase their resistance to flue gas minor components (SO_x and NO_x) and reduce their high synthesis costs and regeneration energy; (ix) Hydrophilic MOF metal nodes, especially those containing transition metals, lower the active site density and compromise the structural integrity of oleophilic processes. Hydrophobic MOFs can be created by grafting oleophilic functions onto open metal sites and choosing hydrophobic linkages. These MOFs will function better because they will keep water molecules out; (x) To evaluate the stability of MOFs, it would be helpful to store them in different atmospheric conditions and track their degradation when exposed to atmospheric oxygen [246].

Fiber optic sensors based on MOFs face a number of challenges, including their stability under a variety of environmental conditions. Unlike some sensing devices that are highly sensitive to moisture, temperature, and mechanical stress, MOFs are more susceptible to external factors that may cause them to degrade in terms of their structural integrity, which, in turn, may affect their performance as sensing devices [157,247]. As environmental conditions change over time or in field-based applications, this issue becomes increasingly evident, altering the behavior of MOFs and reducing their reliability. A second critical challenge remains reproducibility of the synthesis and coating processes for MOFs on optical fibers. In order to ensure consistent and reliable sensor performance, it is crucial to control the morphology, thickness, and uniformity of MOF coatings on fiber surfaces [248]. Nevertheless, scaling up production of these sensors for widespread use is difficult because this process is labor-intensive and complicated, and fabrication techniques often make them less sensitive and selective [249].

It is also important to understand how MOFs interact with target analytes, especially in fiber optic configurations. It remains unclear how MOFs respond, particularly under dynamic and real-world conditions, when integrated with fibers, despite their remarkable tunability [36]. In applications that require multiple analytes to be detected or operations in chemically complex environments, this gap in knowledge hinders the optimization of sensor designs. The performance of MOFs in fiber optic sensors under varying conditions, including the effect of environmental factors, must be explored in more detail to overcome these challenges.

A MOF can improve fiber optic sensor sensitivity, selectivity, and stability, but the field is in its infancy. A variety of sensing applications have benefitted from the development of MOF-based sensors, but several limitations remain that restrict their commercialization and mass production. It is important for future work to focus on improving the long-

term stability of MOFs in order to address these limitations, such as those involving high humidity, acidic or alkaline environments, or extreme temperatures or pressures, as well as those involving high humidity. Using MOFs with multiidentate hydrophobic ligands and strong coordination bonds could be an interesting approach, especially those that involve high-valent metal centers like Ti⁴⁺ and Zr⁴⁺, which have a greater resistance to degradation by the environment when compared to conventional MOFs.

As MOF structures and their structure–property relationships remain unclear, further research is needed to design MOFs with desirable physicochemical properties. In contrast, semiconductive MOFs have been developed using planar and two-dimensional conjugated ligands with redox-active sites. However, the mechanisms underlying host–guest interactions remain unclear. There may be advantages to employing techniques used in the development of semiconductors, such as heteroatom doping, strain engineering, defect modification, and compositing with other conductive materials, in order to improve the performance of MOF-based sensors. A chemiresistive MOF-based sensor with improved charge transport properties could be developed using these approaches at a low cost.

In addition, MOF-based sensors could further improve their sensing capabilities by combining more advanced transduction architectures with multifunctional MOFs of optimal porosity and dimension [250]. It remains challenging, however, because MOFs must be integrated into fiber optic sensing systems in order to be fully exploited. A crucial step in the evolution of MOF-based sensors would be the development of algorithms that allow sensors to self-calibrate, detect anomalies, and predict their lifespans through machine learning. From environmental monitoring to biomedical diagnostics, these sensors could be more adaptable and reliable with such technologies.

There is also a lack of standardized metrics and testing protocols for evaluating the performance of MOF-based fiber optic sensors. The lack of consistent and agreed-upon evaluation standards hinders the progress of the field and complicates the scaling-up of sensor technology, making it difficult to compare sensors across studies. Furthermore, a sophisticated model that encapsulates the interactions between the porous structure of MOFs, their optical properties, and the light propagating through optical fibers is required to be developed that can accurately capture the interactions between the porous structure of MOFs, their optical properties, and the light propagating through optical fibers. As a result of oversimplifying these interactions to a great extent in current models, their predictive power as well as their ability to guide experimental work effectively tends to be limited.

In order to meet these challenges, further research must build on the progress made so far, while also addressing existing gaps in knowledge and technology. In order to unlock the full potential of MOFs in fiber optic sensing, researchers must overcome these limitations, which will allow them to develop advanced sensors suitable for a wide range of applications, including environmental monitoring, industrial diagnostics, and biomedical analysis. Owing to their recent commercial success, MOF materials have a promising future for their potential application because they can compete with current industrial activity and selectivity. Despite being relatively new in this subfield, MOF polymerization materials have not yet achieved commercialization and use in industrial processes. Whereas, MOF materials have generally achieved commercialization. So far, MOFs' high cost has prevented them from replacing traditional adsorbents in environmental applications. However, as the industry grows, new industries will inevitably enter the market to sell less well-known MOFs, which will inevitably open the door for MOFs to be used in realistic environmental applications.

8. Conclusion

There is no doubt that metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) are different from most other 2D materials simply because they are

characterized by exceptional structural diversity, which is due to the self-assembly of molecular building blocks that combine metal nodes and organic linkers to form a molecular structure. Due to the unique properties of MOFs and their derivatives, there has been significant research interest in MOFs and their derivatives, in turn offering immense potential for a wide range of optical applications. Among these technologies are gas sensors, chemical sensors, biosensors, photodetectors, visible light communication (VLC), optical modulators, as well as illumination and display solutions. A key application of MOFs to 2D photonic components is the ability to integrate MOFs to provide a synergistic relationship between the inherent properties of the 2D MOFs and their use in optoelectronic devices, paving the way for advanced technological advancements.

It has been demonstrated that 2D MOFs have incredible potential for applications in photonics and optoelectronics since they take advantage of the distinct structural advantages they offer. In spite of the fact that there is currently an active research program aimed at guiding the controlled synthesis of 2D MOFs with tailored optical and photonic properties, there are still significant challenges to overcome. There is no such thing as a perfect framework material synthesis strategy at this point in time because there is not yet enough control over the assembly process to be able to produce such precision as is necessary in the organic synthesis of materials. There is the limitation that the framework cannot be completely controlled by the researcher and this limits the reproducibility and scalability of the structure in question.

Since 2D MOFs have demonstrated that they possess distinct structural advantages that have made them particularly effective as photonics and optoelectronics materials, there has been substantial research that has demonstrated their potential for applications in these areas. Even though already there is a research program that is actively engaged in the production of 2D MOFs with tailored optical and photonic properties and which aims to guide their controlled synthesis, there are still significant challenges that must be overcome to make this technology a reality. In the current state of organic synthesis, it is impossible to come up with a perfect framework for synthesising materials because there is still a lack of control over the assembly process, so it is not currently possible to achieve the precision needed to produce materials with the level of precision which is needed in organic synthesis. In addition, there is another issue that needs to be addressed, which is the fact that the framework cannot be completely controlled by the researcher. This limits both the reproducibility and scalability of the design in question [251].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jyoti: . **Taposhree Dutta**: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Prabhat Kumar**: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Richa Jangra**: Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Anuj Kumar Sharma**: Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Megha Singh**: Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Pavan Chaturvedi**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Sonika Sharma**: Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Manas Ranjan Garita**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Jyotsna Sharma**: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Satyendra K. Mishra**: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.160543>.

Data availability

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